

SILK ROAD ART AND ARCHAEOLOGY

7

C. Bautze-Picron,
Between Śākyamuni and Vairocana :
Mārīcī, Goddess of Light and Victory

2001

Journal of the Institute of Silk Road Studies, Kamakura

Between Śākyamuni and Vairocana : Mārīcī, Goddess of Light and Victory

Claudine Bautze-Pieron

to the memory of Albert Le Bouheir

The Enlightenment which Śākyamuni achieved at Bodh Gayā has been a central theme in the Buddhist iconography all through its history in the Indian subcontinent.¹ A clear rupture was drawn in the understanding of this event during the post-Gupta period, as it is particularly illustrated in the caves 11 & 12 at Ellora. The narrative dimension is hence excluded from the representation and replaced by an iconic image. This tendency got emphasized in Bihar at the same time when the stela, which is the iconic image *per excellentia*, practically became the only object of worship (in fact, the image became then "icono-narrative").

Notwithstanding the structural changes of the image, the subject of the nocturnal fight between Śākyamuni and Māra remained a major iconographic topic illustrated by a number of images, dating upto the 12th c.² But, since the Buddha was the sole icon of the stela, since the representation of the solitary monk seated below the tree was favoured to any other one, it became necessary to find a new way for illustrating the mystery of the Enlightenment. This way was to multiply images of "deities" who belong to the drama which this event was, for their existence can only be justified through the Bodhi. These deities had various destinies : Vasudhārā remained part of the image of the Buddha, arising out of the earth below the latter but other characters were represented separately. Thus, Yamāntaka would become a major Krodha in Tibetan Buddhism, Aparājitā was, on the contrary, to be worshipped only in Magadha (her images were collected from Nālandā upto Bodh Gayā via Tetrāvāñ) and Uṣṇīsavijayā held a similar limited position in this context³ whereas Mārīcī would be offered a more important position and cult in Magadha and in the region of Vikrampur in south-east Bangladesh as well as in Orissa.

Although a large part of these images were noticed in Orissa, one has to admit, none the less, that, in contrary to the rich iconographical developments in Bihar or Bengal, the iconography is in this region limited to a reduced number of forms which apparently trace their origin in Bihar. Beyond India, rare images of Mārīcī will be found in Nepal and Tibet where they arrived as a contemporary and later development of the situation noticed in eastern India, as well in Japan where she is known as "Marishi-ten (摩利支天)" as in China where her depictions were even realised till the recent centuries. It is also in Chinese that is preserved probably the earliest testimony of the existence of the goddess since a text entitled *Mo-li-chih-t'ien-ching* was most

probably translated during the first part of the 6th century: it mentions offerings being made to her and is also "devoted to the benefit which one would receive from reciting this dhāraṇī". An enlarged version was translated in the 8th century by Amoghavajra, mentioning that "small images of the deity (should be carried) on the head or on the arms as amulets."

Mārīcī in the Research

Mārīcī has already been the topic of various studies. **Alfred Foucher** was the first scholar to publish in 1905 different *sādhanas* devoted to the goddess by comparing them with images known to him. He introduced a path which was followed by **Benoytosh Bhattacharyya** in 1924 and 1958 and by **Bhagwan Sahai** in 1975. Their method was to propose a typology of the available literary descriptions and to identify the artistic images through the texts. It was also the way of working of **R.O. Meisezahl** and of **Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann** who considered the goddess in their research on Vajravārāhī. In her last book, published in 1976, the French authoress proposed a clear presentation of the information gathered in the *Sādhanamālā* and other sources including information related to iconography.⁵

The work of **Siegfried Behrsing**, published in 1943, opens a new way since the author makes a typology of the images of the goddess through the mean of two criteria, i.e. the number of faces and the one of arms. This allows him, though still in a rudimentary manner, to propose a correlation between the frequency of the different types and the geographic origin of the images.

The writings of **D.C. Bhattacharyya** show also new perspectives even though most of the author's conclusions are highly debatable.⁶ He tries to restore the historical context in which the image of the goddess could have found its formulation, but his arguments are very specious: one cannot admit that this formulation was the mere result of the conceptual and iconographic equivalence which this image might have had with the images and the personality of Sūrya on the one hand or that it was understood to be a "solar aspect of the Devī or Śakti" on the other hand. Bhattacharyya tries, as much as he can, to introduce Mārīcī in the Hindu pantheon and this on the basis of general assumptions which do not trace their origin in a scientific study of the material but in a rather vague, and political, position of collecting as much images of the Buddhist pantheon as possible as being indeed Hindu. Besides, the goddess would owe some aspects of her iconography, more particularly the seven sows or her animal face, to the necessity, for Buddhism, to assimilate elements of popular belief which would have penetrated into Buddhism through the siddhas. Within this perspective, but with more accuracy as to the intricate relation with the solar god, **Janice Leoshko** recently proposed to relate the personality of the goddess and the elaboration of her image with the particular moment which was the Enlightenment, when the complete universe was penetrated with the solar light; she underlined the relations between the images of Mārīcī and Sūrya and located the origin of the image of the goddess at Bodhi Gayā.⁷ Even more recently, Mallar Mitra provided a precise description of images preserved in museums of Calcutta, relating

them eventually to the relevant *sādhanas*.

Those various studies introduce two different perspectives, first they propose a typology of the plastic and literary images and identify the ones with the help of the other ones, second they try to identify the sources of Mārīcī's iconography. None the less, one is forced to admit that they do not pay a great attention, if at all, to the historical development of the iconography. The aim of the present paper is also not to follow in a detailed manner the chronological development of both types of images, plastic and literary, but rather to make an attempt in bringing into light the appearance of this deity, underlying the probable concepts which sustained both this appearance and the aspects which it took. However, it is evident that this approach has to rely on a historical reading of the iconographical development.

The chronological analysis of the goddess's images is precious since it allows to consider various aspects of her iconography and her personality which the texts do not present. The stylistic analysis permits to constitute groups of images around stelae, the provenance of which is known and allows to follow their chronology. In this way, a historical line is drawn, around which the iconographical study can be clearly stated. Beyond this study, which will be here summed up, we will have to consider the meaning of some "iconographical" motifs belonging to the image of Mārīcī, which would allow to come closer to the goddess's personality and to account simultaneously for the elaboration of her image and for her position within the Buddhist pantheon. We shall only shortly consider the representations of Aśokakāntā Mārīcī, as she is named in *sādhanas*, who stands or sits as an attending figure to the Tārā and who is only but rarely depicted as main icon. Her iconography is simple since the goddess presents a peaceful human form, holding the branch of the tree to which she owes her name.

History of Mārīcī Images

A. In art

a. Bodh Gayā

The oldest images nowadays known were recovered at Bodh Gayā, they can be dated in the 9th & 10th c. (appendix 1-12, figs. 1-2) - but images must have already been made at least one century earlier, as we saw in the introduction. These images were most probably amulets, perhaps made of clay, and since the ritual focalizing on the goddess, include then the making of the *maṇḍala* together with the recitation of the *dhāraṇī*, it involves the existence of an "esoteric" trend which preceded the "exoteric" one when images are carved and offered to the worship. But more than that perhaps, it illustrates also the use of white magic by the monk (since *dhāraṇīs* were made for a very practical use). A much erased stela from Itkhauri, a site located south-east from Bodh Gayā, also belongs to this group (app. 13, fig. 3). Mārīcī is six-armed, stands in *alidhāsana* on a chariot which is drawn by a group of animals outlined in the lower part of the stela; these are either seven horses, or seven sows observed in other sites (below); the presence of the horses underlines the

link with Sūrya's iconography. The animals can be profiled in one single direction (fig. 2) or constitute two divergent groups, of respectively three and four animals which are arranged symmetrically on either side of Rāhu's head (fig. 1). This last choice reflects the rule of symmetry which constitutes a fundamental criterion for elaborating the stela. The ateliers of Nālandā will preserve this type of grouping, drawing the profile of the seventh sow on the central part of the pedestal, eventually hidden by Rāhu (but the latter is generally trampled by the animal).

The following distribution of attributes is noticed : the *vajra* and the branch of *aśoka* are presented in the raised right and left hands, the arrow in the second right hand, which is symmetric to the bow in the left hand and the needle held in the third right hand, usually lying on the thigh, with the noose often combined with the gesture of threat (*tarjanīmudrā*).

The three faces, among which one will be the one of a sow, constitute a further typical feature of the goddess concerning which the artists appeared to have hesitated at Bodh Gayā and at Kurkihār (below). As a matter of fact, the animal face is distributed on the proper right (figs. 2-3) or left side (app. 2) or on either side (fig. 4, app. 9) when it is not simply ignored with three human faces being carved (fig. 1). This diversity, which is not encountered at Nālandā where the sow face is carved on the proper left side (below), could well indicate a phase of iconographic creativity when attempts are being made in various directions; these sculptures are also the most ancient ones known illustrating Mārīcī. The stelae reproducing the goddess with three human faces (fig. 1) or with the animal face on the proper right side (app. 1 & 11, fig. 2) are also stylistically close to the production of the Kurkihār atelier in the 9th c. On the other side, those where the sow face is on the proper left side are later and closer to the art of Nālandā and the region in the 10th c. (app. 2).

b. Kurkihār

Kurkihār, located on the road between Nālandā and Bodh Gayā, still remains an unresearched (but unfortunately looted) site. From the 7th century and onwards, the worship centered itself on the image of the Buddha at the time of His Enlightenment and on the representations of Avalokiteśvara and of the Tārā. The images of Mārīcī remained rare; the few stelae illustrating the goddess which can be attributed to the local production, reflect the dichotomy noticed at Bodh Gayā (figs. 4-5 : app. 14-15). The second image (fig. 5) is related to the iconography of Nālandā (below) : face of the sow on the proper left, eight-armed (not six-armed), female attendants with sow faces who are distributed around the central deity, presence of the *caitya* within which the goddess stands. However, the selection of attributes does not coincide with the one generalized at Nālandā since the sword, so evident in the Nālandā images, is here absent (the goad might have been held in the second right hand, now broken). The first image is even more peculiar (fig. 4) : two faces of sow are profiled, the goddess stands in *pratyaliḍhāsana*, her crown supports a *caitya* and not Vairocana. On the other stela from Kurkihār, the Jina was present although he did not display his more traditional gesture of teaching but the one of meditation.⁸⁾ It should be noticed here that the ateliers of Bodh Gayā had not yet fixed this iconographical question since many

images do not include any representation of Vairocana at all. The rule of introducing a tiny image of the Jina, teaching, at the top of the stela or within a medallion adorning the tiara, got implemented at Nālandā.

c. Nālandā, Ghosrāvān and Tetrāvān

A large number of images were recovered at Nālandā (app. 17-30, figs. 6-10) and in the region, at Ghosrāvān and Tetrāvān (app. 31-32, figs. 14 & 15). The goddess always presents the same position, is three-faced with the animal face on the proper left side (with a rare example of two side animal faces : app. 20, fig. 7) and is eight-armed. Beside the attributes noticed at Bodh Gayā or Kurkihār, the *aṅkuśa* is added in one of the left hands and the sword is held in the raised right hand. Mārīcī stands very often in a *cāitya* : the upper part of the back-slab is adorned with *aśoka* branches which fall on either side of the reduced representation of a *sikhara* (app. 18, 24-26, figs. 6 & 9).

The artists of Nālandā broadened the iconography of the goddess, they stressed her affiliation to Vairocana with the representation of the latter at the top of the stela or in the tiara, they visualized her surrounded by a field of flames (figs. 8 & 10) or they gave her female attendants showing the face of a sow. Three groups of images can be listed :

1° the attending figures are absent (only a woman driver can be drawn in the foreground : app. 22, 31, 32, figs. 14 & 15),

2° the attendants are two-armed (app. 18, 23, 25, figs. 6-8),

3° the same are four-handed (app. 24). This last form appears in Bengal in 11th & 12th c. (below). The artists modified also the treatment of some attributes : the arrow is not necessarily held in a hand but is drawn out of the quiver which stands beneath Mārīcī's feet (figs. 14 & 15, app. 30); the rule of symmetry, which is fundamental in the elaboration of the image, can prescribe the introduction of a second quiver (fig. 14). As to Rāhu's face, it can slip below the animals of the chariot (app. 22, 24).

Most of these images can be dated in the 10th, or even 11th c. They can measure nearly one meter or only a few centimeters, having thus been worshipped in public as well as privately. Beside these stone images, some bronzes are known (app. 48-50, fig. 16) which appear to have been cast in the region of Nālandā : the goddess is eight-armed and presents the *vajra* in place of the sword in the upper right hand.

d. East Bihar

The only known image discovered at Lakhi Sarai, which can be dated in the 12th c., finds its roots in this group and in the earlier one at Kurkihār and Bodh Gayā (app. 33, fig. 17). This stela integrates the attendants distributed in a circle around the goddess, all standing in a landscape of flames. Mārīcī is eight-armed but does not show the sword, Vairocana sits at the top of the slab. A second image, the present whereabouts of which are unknown, was photographed in the late 19th

c. in the neighbouring village of Uren (app. 34).

e. Bengal

Beyond Bihar, some images were carved in the 11th and 12th c. in north Bengal (app. 35-36, fig. 18) whereas at Vikrampur and Mainamati, or in a wider area in south-east Bangladesh, a very large number of Mārīcī's representations have been collected (app. 37-46, figs. 19-20). They all illustrate the same iconography where the *caitya* is carved in a very evident manner, forming a niche within which the goddess stands surrounded by her four attendants: two branches of *aśoka* fall on either side of the *śikhara*.

Since numerous images of the goddess were discovered in **south-east Bangladesh** (39-47), it is rather easy to underline the distinctive iconographic features, which characterize them in comparison with those noticed on the few images collected in **north Bengal** (35-38). In both region, the four female attendants are four-armed and present the face of the sow (an exception is illustrated by 42). In the southern region, they usually stand on the ground with two of them profiled on either side of the goddess and with two carved between the legs of the latter (39, 40, 41, 43, 45, 46; fig. 19) or, more rarely, with only one of them at this position whereas the fourth one hovers above Mārīcī's head (44, 47; fig. 20). These images do not adorn the goddess with the *upavīta*: indeed, only two images from the region integrate the ornament (44, 47). The two features peculiar to these images are observed in the images from the northern region (35-38; fig. 18), which allows to suggest a direct relation between them. The spatial distribution of the four goddesses around Mārīcī is evidently borrowed from Bihar: on images from Nālandā, two such attendants are profiled on either side of the goddess whereas a female driver sits between the latter's legs (fig. 8) or three can be depicted, the third one hovering above Mārīcī (fig. 6), which implies that the seated female driver is intended to be the fourth attendant (see also 24). An image from Kurkihār (fig. 5) and the later stela from Lakhi Sarai (fig. 17) offer a "clearer" illustration of the group since four small goddesses are symmetrically distributed around Mārīcī whereas the coach woman sits in front of the latter and it is probably in these rare examples from Bihar that one has to trace the origin of the iconographic setting of the Bengali images. They served as a model which was not always very well understood as the image from Ujani proves it (42): this stela integrates five anonymous human figures all standing in an aggressive mood, each of them holding the *vajra*; the animals of the vehicle form the traditional frieze covering the pedestal but there exists no connection between them and the deities standing above them; this image illustrates an extreme simplification of the iconography which is also perceptible in the stylistic rendering.

Like on these stelae from Kurkihār and Lakhi Sarai also, the goddess preserves in Bengal the thunderbolt in place of the sword in the raised right hand. This weapon forms a pair with the branch of *aśoka*, the second pair includes the arrow and the bow, the third one the *anikuśa* and the gesture of threat, the fourth one the needle and the noose held by the hands which lie on the thighs. Vairocana appears alone (40, 46; fig. 20) or at the centre of the group of Tathāgatas in the upper

part of t

f. Ori

A very
the ico
concom
(app. 6
wherea
situatio
single
mount

Imag
unique
of *aśo*
see th
goad.
four c
58) is
Like
(app.

Sto
the 1
85, 8
fierce
tiger-
usua
occu
pair
even

B. I

The
be v
plas
sād
whi
god

part of the stela (app. 36 & 39).

f. Orissa and other regions

A very large number of Mārīcī's images have been carved in Orissa (app. 51-78). On the whole, the iconography is uniform and is related to the one encountered in Bihar. We observe the concomitance of the three human faces and of the chariot drawn by horses on stelae from Ratnagiri (app. 63-68, 76-77) and Salihundam (app. 55), as it was the case on some images from Bodh Gayā, whereas the presence of one animal face coincides with the seven sows drawing the chariot. In both situations, the goddess is six-armed. The group of eight-armed images is later (app. 57-60); one single example is known from Ratnagiri (app. 73) and Mārīcī's legs can be partly hidden by the mount (app. 57, 60, 63).

Images are very often damaged, arms are broken and the attributes have disappeared. However, a unique structure seems to have prevailed. In the left hands, we notice the rope, the bow, the flower of *aśoka* and with the gesture of threat, the noose (in the hand on the thigh). In the right hands, we see the needle (in the hand on the thigh), the thunderbolt (in the raised hand), the arrows and the goad. These images can also integrate the four attendants, all four-handed and distributed in the four quarters (app. 57 & 58) whereas only one single example, perhaps from Uttar Pradesh (app. 58) is known where the attendants are two-armed and form two groups on either side of Mārīcī. Like a number of representations of the goddess in Orissa, the only known image from Sārnāth (app. 51) is apparently based on a prototype from Bodh Gayā.

Stone and bronze images differ from the representations noticed in manuscript illuminations of the 11th & 12th c. from Bihar, most probably from the region of Nālandā or Lakṣī Sarai (app. 81-85, 89-91), from Nepal (app. 87-88) or east Bengal (app. 86) where the goddess usually presents a fierce aspect which had remained ignored by the sculptors : Mārīcī is pot-bellied and clad with a tiger-skin. Due most probably to the limited space made available, the animals of the chariot are usually absent. In this form, she would appear as early as the beginning of the 11th c. since she occurs in the manuscript from Nepal dated A.D. 1015 (app. 87). As such also, she usually forms a pair with Parṇasabarī (app. 83, 85, 86), appears in the vicinity of Vasudhārā (app. 83 & 87) or is even directly related to the Buddha (app. 91).

B. In the sādhanas

The *Sādhanamālā* includes a large number of texts (132 to 147) describing images which should be visualized; the information which they contain can be compared to a certain degree with the plastic material and is summarized at the end of this paper. We shall here only mention that no *sādhana* in this collection concerns a six-armed form (noticed at Bodh Gayā or Kurkihār, and which is described in the *maṇḍala* 17 of the *Niṣpannayogāvalī*) but that five texts describe the goddess with eight arms (134, 137, 142 & 146; 144); the first four texts quote the animal face

whereas the fifth one does not do it but describes the feelings which the three heads should express. As a matter of fact, the first four texts all refer to a same image: the goddess should be visualized surrounded by attendants and Rāhu drives the chariot which is drawn by seven sows. The fifth and last text (144) details not only the nine feelings of the faces, it also describes the functions of the attributes and lets the goddess trample on Prajñā and the Upāya (for details, see below). The eight-armed form is noticed at Nālandā but the sword, which is a prominent attribute in this iconography is not accounted for in these texts (but in those related to the twelve-armed deity).

A two-armed form is described in the texts 133 and 141 where she has her flower as attribute and displays the gesture of generosity, being visualized above a sow. Two texts concern the ten-armed form (132 & 135); she has (logically) five faces, including the head of the sow, is accompanied by assistants, drives on a chariot drawn by the seven sows which trample above the Navagrahas (135). Quite interesting is the presence, among her attributes of the *candramaṇḍala* and of the *srūyamaṇḍala* which are added to the attributes of the eight-armed form.

Five texts introduce a twelve-armed form (136, 138, 139, 140, 143). It is six-headed, including the sow-face which should be black: each face presents a different colour. This image imparts a general feeling of fright. The goddess carries weapons such as the sword, the arrow, the axe e.g., she also presents the cut head of Brahmā. A goddess draws her chariot and she tramples in one case (145) above Hindu deities (Harihara, Brahmā, Lokapālas) (see Appendix).

The visualization of the deity follows a pattern which is encountered in most of the *sādhana*s. After having brought in his heart the vacuity, *śūnyatā*, the monk starts his meditation where he progressively visualizes elements arising out of each other; the number of elements can vary but the final part of the visualization is common to all *sādhana*s. At a certain point, the monk visualizes the red branch or bud of the *aśoka* (*aśokaśtava*, *aśokapallava*) from where the red or yellow syllable *mām* (*rakta/pītamāṅkāram*) emerges, and from this very letter, the deity will arise. A first visualization of the same letter may also have taken place before the evocation of the tree.

Particular Images of Mārīcī

Some representations of Mārīcī are peculiar inasmuch as they are not isolated images but evidently belong to a larger iconographic context. Such is the case of the two goddess's images seen at the bottom of the Jagdīśpur stela (app. 26 & 27, figs. 9 & 10) or of those carved on slabs from Bodh Gayā (app. 4-5). Further, an image like the one of Bhavanipur offers an extremely rare and rather enigmatic aspect of the deity (app. 47, fig. 21). This chapter will be concluded with the study of painted representations of the deity, which introduce evidently new aspects unknown in sculpture.

1. The slabs from Bodh Gayā, the stela at Jagdīśpur/Nālandā.

The goddess is closely related to the Enlightenment of Śākyamuni as two slabs from Bodh Gayā

illustrate it. The first slab includes a long inscription in Chinese, dated A.D. 1021-1022. Two symmetric divergent images of Mārīcī are carved on either side of the Buddha calling the Earth. The second slab is damaged but apparently reproduced the very same iconography (app. 4 & 5).

The same observation applies to the two side panels of the pedestal of the large Jagdīśpur stela: they are not visible when one faces the image, which might explain why they remained ignored till recently. These two panels (app. 26 & 27, figs. 9 & 10) have thus an intermediary position between the scene of Māra's attack and the representation of the Aṣṭamahābodhisattvas (fig. 11).⁹⁹

The presence of the Bodhisattvas and of the five Jinas in the upper part of the image, partakes in a coherent manner of the iconographic program illustrated by this stela. The first ones observe the last life of the Buddha, the latter ones are at the source of this descent. From the Jinas/Tathāgatas to the Buddha, passing through the Bodhisattvas, it is thus the triple body of Buddhism which would be illustrated, from the primary *dharmakāya*, distributed to the five directions, to the *nirmaṇakāya* of the eight Bodhisattvas and to the *sambhogakāya* of the historical Buddha, whose biography is essentially illustrated by eight great events at the time. The stela of Jagdīśpur can also be read as being a *maṇḍala* the central axis of which passes through Śākyamuni at His Enlightenment; the Buddha is depicted as a monk but carries also the tiara which is carved hiding the lower part of the three branches of the pipal tree which arises above the nimbus. This axis ends in Vairocana, the only one among the Tathāgatas to wear the diadem and to be adorned with jewels (fig. 13). As to the lower part of the image, it constitutes the seat on which the Buddha defeats Māra whose army attacks the holy man. On this background of confusion, the shape of the Buddha shows peace. The relief carved below the Buddha and which illustrates Māra and his daughters reflects a similar confusion which is balanced by the peaceful depiction of the Bodhisattvas.

Whereas the male figures of the Jinas, of the Buddha and of the Bodhisattvas display peace and calm, the female deities introduce movement and dynamics within the stela, be they Aparājītā trampling on Gaṇapati or the two forms of Mārīcī on the side panels (figs. 9 & 10). Such a dynamic energy differs from the passivity which is usually shown by the Prajñā in Buddhism, in contrary to the active Śakti of Hinduism. Both panels reproduce Mārīcī in the most known form on the right side and in an utmost rare representation on the left side : indeed, she stands on a cremation ground, is twelve-armed and has six fierce faces. Numerous attributes can be identified : in the right hands, the sword, the pestle, the arrow and the hatchet as well as perhaps the thunderbolt and a further indistinct attribute and in the left hands, the goad, the bow, the flower of *aśoka*, the head (of Brahmā), perhaps the trident and the noose which would be held by the hand displaying the *tarjanīmudrā* in front of the breast. This image is similar to the Vajradhātviśvarī of *sādhanas* 136 or to the Oḍiyānamārīcī described in *sādhanas* 138-140 & 143.¹⁰⁰

The main scene of the Jagdīśpur stela reproduces the event of Bodh Gayā with a great attention given to the members of Māra's army. Among them, different Hindu deities are introduced, in particularly, in what concerns our present topic, a goddess having the face of a sow (fig. 12).

Sitting on the buffalo, she is very probably Vārāhī who belongs to the group of the Mothers. The goddess is four-handed presenting the knife, the skull, the goad and in the upper right hand an object similar to the horse-radish. The last two attributes are thus apparently borrowed from Gaṇeśa's iconography whereas the first two ones belongs to the plastic iconography of Vajravārāhī.¹¹ Why Vārāhī ? why this Mother ? The seven Mothers occur twice in the *maṇḍalas* of the *Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa* and of the *Mahāvairocanasūtra/Vairocanābhisambodhitantra*.¹² They should be painted in the southern quarter where they accompany Yama, god of the dead. And Yama, we cannot ignore it, is identified with Māra at this period.¹³ The closeness to Yama is also underlined through the presence of the buffalo, vehicle of the Hindu god. But could all these various elements be enough to justify the presence of Vārāhī and not of any other Mother in the army attacking Śākyamuni ? The knife and the skull belong in particular to the two frightening deities Vajravārāhī and Viḥnāntaka.¹⁴ To be short, we would face here a intricate personality : Vārāhī would have been selected for her similarities with Yama (the buffalo), but she integrates also two of the attributes belonging to Gaṇeśa (the *anikuśa* and the *mūlaka*) and two which will be constantly included in the iconography of Vajravārāhī, i.e. the *kapāla* held in the left hand and which she seems to raise to her lips (as Vajravārāhī does) and the *kartrī* in a right hand.

We should also remember that Gaṇeśa holds a negative position in the mythology of the Enlightenment, a position which justifies the function of the Krodha Viḥnāntaka, in charge of destroying the elephant-headed god. Vajravārāhī shares her face of sow with Mārīcī, even though the animal face constitutes an excrescence above one of the ears whereas it is completely included within the facial composition of the second goddess. Thus, this deity on the Jagdi-pur stela includes simultaneously the pair of attributes which are commonly held by Vajravārāhī and the face of sow which characterizes Mārīcī.

2. The stela of Bhavanipur

This image (app. 47, fig. 21) was recovered at Bhavanipur, in the region of Dhaka where it was most probably imported from Bihar. Its identification has not yet been clearly made, as a partly result of the damaged back-slab; most of the attributes held by the left hands are thus lost. Most scholars agreed, none the less, on the identification of the deity with Mahāpratisarā, one of the Pañcaraksās.¹⁵

Stylistic considerations allow to attribute the carving of this image to ateliers which were located around Ghosrāvān/Tetrāvān/Nālandā (figs. 14-15) :

- large round back-slab, the edge of which is adorned with the pearled garland and with the flames shaped as question marks;
- architectural pedestal with successive recesses, with two diverging grimacing lions;
- diadem adorned with a series of circular and diamond-shaped medallions;
- necklace with a large central gem which occurs, in a similar shape, at the girdle; armlets including a large stone surrounded by scrolls (similar structure at the necklace and the girdle);

loops attached to the armlets:

- long plain skirt (folds are not indicated) which is adorned with incised flowers;
- broad flap of cloth falling on the left hip.

The round and full shapes of the limbs, the elegant movement of the body, the accomplished equilibrium between the detailed ornamentation and the plain surfaces, between the line and the volume, are further criteria characterizing the art of Nālandā and the region in the second half of the 10th c.

In the two Mārīcī images from Ghosrāvān/Tetrāvān (figs. 14-15) and on this sculpture, the goddess holds an arrow out of the quiver put on her proper right. A broad flame is carved on the back-slab above her and the very same shape occurs not only on these two images but also on some from Nālandā (app. 25). The goddess wears the tiara which adorns Mārīcī, with successive recesses and adorned with medallions bearing representations of the Tathāgatas. On the frontpart, two superimposed medallions illustrate a Jina meditating below a second one who is depicted as teaching(?), a gesture which reappears in the proper left side medallion with the gesture of touching the earth on the proper right side. It might be, therefore, possible to recognize in all cases Vairocana whose two gestures are those of the meditation and, more often, of the teaching (which replaces the *bodhyagrīmudrā*).

Three faces are visible, only the front one smiles whereas the right face is distorted by a cruel expression of the mouth and by a wrinkled forehead above wide-opened eyes (figs.21-a) and the left face displays a more severe one although the half-opened mouth expresses slightly smiles (fig.21-b). Whereas Mārīcī generally has an animal face, its evident oblivion here is not an exception since some stelae from Bodh Gayā and Nālandā (fig. 1, app. 18) also show the same salient feature which is testified in the texts.⁶⁹ But the multiple feelings which these three faces here illustrate, remind of the nine sentiments which the three faces of Mārīcīpicuvā have to display according to the *sādhana* 144.

This text attributes to the central face terrifying feelings whereas in the plastic illustrations, these expressions are always shown by the side faces. As a matter of fact, the main face is peaceful, often smiling while the other two faces can illustrate violent expressions. On the whole, however, only a few images of the goddess with three human faces are known since the sow face gets generalized as soon as it appears at Nālandā. In this case, the human face which is on the proper right side can show a peaceful expression or be more severe if not be distorted (by anger?). The Berlin (fig. 1) and Dhaka images show three human faces, illustrating the same feelings which can better analysed in the light of the information provided by the *sādhana*. The main face would show *karuṇā*, *śānta* and *adbhūta*, the proper left face would illustrate *vīra*, *śyṅgāra* and *hāṣya*, the proper right one *bibhātsa*, *raudra* and *bhayānaka*.⁷⁰ This distribution of the functions among the three faces could coincide with the functions of the goddess's attributes, which are also mentioned in the literary sources since to attack evil spirits, it is not only heroism but also joy which is required to give battle to the enemy. It is fitting to frighten those wicked goblins, which explains

also why the deity is stamped with aversion or with wrath in front of them. But is she also not the one who blesses them when they are tamed, with her flower of *aśoka*, showing thus her compassion? As a matter of fact, this multiplicity of expressions and feelings, although divergent at times, helps to precise the position of Mārīcī within the Buddhist pantheon. She stands at the limit between two worlds, the chaotic universe of the damned, diabolic crowd of Māra's army, who disturbs and threatens the peaceful and clear way towards Enlightenment. In this perspective, Mārīcī has a highly protecting function, similar to the one of the Pañcarakṣās, she acts like the Krodhas, fighting the evil through the means of evil: she defends with strength and violence the Buddhist path, but when the wicked goblins are vanquished, she offers them her face of compassion and of serenity, aspects of that very path. Mārīcī appears thus here as an image of transition between the outer dark world and the inner bright one.

The same texts which ignore the animal face, also describe the goddess with eight arms and three faces - which corresponds to what is seen on the Dhaka image. Mārīcīpicuvā is little known, only the *sādhana* 144 is dedicated to her, but it is an extremely precious text since it does not only mention that the goddess rides rough-shod over the Upāya and the Prajñā, but also describes the function of her eight attributes.¹⁸¹

The deity from Bhavanipur presents on the proper right side the raised sword, a stick topped with a half-thunderbolt (attribute of Ubhayavarāhānanamārīcī)¹⁸⁰ and pulls the arrow out of the quiver; the fourth raised hand is broken but seems to have held an attribute of small size which was perhaps the needle or *sūci*. In the proper left hands, she holds the thunderbolt on the thigh and in the following raised hand the *ānikuśa*, the lower part of which is still visible. The two remaining hands, now broken, probably held the emblematic flower, the *aśoka* and the bow together with the noose, still visible. It is, however, also possible, although the relation is not clear, that this attribute was related to the thunderbolt: the noose with handles shaped as *vajras* is mentioned as being an attribute of a Pañcarakṣā, Mahāpratisarā or, what is here more relevant, of a frightening aspect of Mārīcī named Ubhayavarāhānanamārīcī.²⁰

The torso is shifted towards the right, with a movement full of force which reproduces the hardness of Mārīcī when she stands; the deity sits here in *sattvaparyāyikāsana* above a lotus which is spread on the pedestal where the two diverging lions, strongly reminding of the same ones carved at Nālandā, frame a panel where Gaṇeśa is crouching, the right hand raised towards the goddess in a possible gesture of prayer which he also shows when Aparājītā treads him down under her feet. Behind him, an emaciated figure shows a grinning face. It is possible that he and Gaṇeśa represent the Obstacles which Aparājītā or Parīaśabarī destroy, or they may illustrate both the Upāya and the Prajñā mentioned in the text as being crushed by Mārīcī.²¹ Thus, the Dhaka image illustrates most probably an aspect of Mārīcī, which is not described as such in the available iconographic literature but which gathers elements found in various *sādhana*s. The goddess is depicted, with a majestic and dignified bearing as the position of her legs or the slightly arched torso betray. With her main left arm lying above the thigh and the corresponding right hand raised,

she shows force and dynamism and since she holds in these two hands the thunderbolt and the sword, she illustrates at best the activity of the *prajñā* dissipating at the moment of Enlightenment the darkness and the illusion.²⁵¹ since the sword can also be named *prajñākhaḍga* when it is held by Mañjuśrī in the very same position shown by Mārīcī.²⁵²

3. The painted versions of Mārīcī : the fierce Goddess

A number of painted manuscripts include representations of the goddess which were not illustrated in sculpture. As a matter of fact, apart from one painting in the Vredenburg manuscript (fig. 22 - app. 82) where she is six-armed and shows the form which is usually hers in sculpture while standing within the womb of a *caitya*, and one in the Harivarman manuscript preserved at the Varendra Research Museum (app.81) where she is eight-armed, the other illuminations depict the deity in a fierce attitude. Moreover, in this frightening form, she constitutes a pair with Parṇaśabarī.²⁵³ Both of them are depicted together either on a book-cover (85) (figs. 27-28), a single folio (83)(figs. 23-24), or on two folios close to each other (86)(figs. 25-26). An elf-armed version (87)²⁵⁴ shows Mārīcī in a wild mood standing in a flaming background: pot-bellied, she has there three (human) faces.

A further form, which could not be traced in sculpture, apart from the Bhavanipur image, shows the deity seated in *vajrāsana* (app. 91). On these examples, she is eight-armed, three-faced (no information is available for the colour of the faces),²⁵⁵ and is apparently yellow.

A book-cover out of a pair²⁵⁶ includes nine illuminations among which the two depictions of Mārīcī and Parṇaśabarī (figs. 26-27 : 82-M & P), coincide, in their respective position, with Kurukullā and Vajravārāhī on the first board. The central triad shows Mañjuśrī teaching, seated on the black lion; he is surrounded by the complex depictions of two ten-armed female deities who are probably Nāmasaṅgīti (fig. 27). This "cantilena of names" is related here to Mañjuśrī who is the central figure of this cover; this triad illustrates the knowledge and Mañjuśrī, as he is here depicted (i.e. on the lion and teaching), illustrates the word spoken by Śākyamuni at Bodh Gayā.²⁵⁷

Though not illustrated by the presence of the Buddha, the mystery of the Enlightenment would be here depicted through the means of other images. Simultaneously, the *karuṇā* of Avalokiteśvara & of the Tāra -two other major characters on these two boards- is opposed/complementary to the *prajñā* of Mañjuśrī. The Bombay manuscript (91) includes Mārīcī between the depiction of two major events of the Buddha's life, i.e. the offering of the *madhu* by the monkey at Vaiśālī where Śākyamuni decided to renounce to life,²⁵⁸ and the Parinirvāṇa. This "complete extinction" is the fulfilment of the "extinction" which took place at Bodh Gayā when light invaded the universe : this would account for the presence of the deity at this very place, she expresses the light which spreads when the Buddha passes away.²⁵⁹

The central triads compose apparently the point of convergence of the deities distributed on either side: in which case, it is likely that the two terrific female representations on each board acted perhaps simultaneously as gate-keepers of the inner field and as expression of the light

emanating from this field (Mañjuśrī on the lion / Vajratārā).

Some Aspects of Mārīcī

Various iconographic "motifs" are repeatedly noticed in art and in literature, which deserve some attention in this attempt to come to a closer, if not better, knowledge and understanding of the personality of the goddess.

1. The attributes

Like Aparājitā, Mārīcī holds the very peculiar position of defeating the evil minds, for which she wittingly uses her attributes. The *sādhana* 144 is informative concerning this aspect since it details the respective use of the objects held by the goddess. With the bow and the arrow, she pierces the wicked; with the needle and the thread, she sows up their eyes; with the *aṅkuśa*, she strikes their heart; with the noose, she pulls them at their neck; with the thunderbolt, she shatters their heart to pieces and with the flower of *aśoka*, she sprinkles water.³¹)

Like Aparājitā tramples on Gaṇapati or the Navagrahas, Mārīcī can also tread under her chariot the Planets as well as "the personified decess, the death, the hunger and the distress"³²). The latter must probably be identified on two stelae, one of them photographed at Uren (app. 34 & 48) and on an illumination belonging to a manuscript dated in year 17 of Madanapāla's reign (app. 84).

At Bodh Gayā and Kurkihār, the six hands of the goddess present the bow and the arrow, the thunderbolt and the flower of *aśoka*, the needle and the string. From then and onwards, rules are introduced, related to the position of the attributes in the image : the arrow is on the proper right side and the bow is symmetric to it; the thunderbolt is held by the right hand which is raised, ready to hit the wicked whereas the flower is offered in a raised left hand; the needle is shown in the third hand lying above the thigh and the string is held by a left hand which also displays the gesture of threat or *tarjanīmudrā* (hand which is usually carved in front of the breast). The image from San Francisco (fig. 4) shows an interesting reading of this form since it exchanges the positions of the needle and of the flower, which could be a further sign that points to the phase of elaboration of the goddess's iconography. Besides, one notices here clearly that the thread passes through the eye of the needle, which allows to suggest that the two attributes do not only constitute a pair but are combined. This treatment will remain in the later development of the image where the needle, together with the string, is presented by the right hand which lies on the thigh, symmetric to the noose held in the lower left hand.

But what is to be seen on images from Nālandā and the region ? Two new attributes are introduced, the *aṅkuśa* and the sword, a weapon which is not mentioned in the literary sources. As a matter of fact, the sword needs to be added to the list provided by the *sādhana*s since it did not replace any other attribute. It could have replaced the thunderbolt on which it is superposed in plastic imagery. The gesture of hit illustrated by the upper right hand which holds the raised sword

is not pec
this weap
one of the
identified

At Bodh
stretched
preserved
displayed
for direct
The latte
disappea

When
eastern
whereas
of *aśoka*
of threa
presente
the four
seen in
then).
with the

2. Va

Like A
above
womb
upper
carved
rarely
figs. 6
us to
treatm

The
explai
a Buc
the tr
image
The

is not peculiar to Mārīcī since it essentially distinguishes Mañjuśrī. It is also from Nālandā that this weapon, as attribute of the immediate knowledge, will replace in the series of the *saptaratnas* one of the male figures, probably the chief of the army who obviously holds this sword which was identified above as being the *prajñākhadga*.³⁵

At Bodh Gayā and Kurkihār, Mārīcī is six-armed and the *vajra* is held in the right hand which is stretched in order to hit the evil and to break their heart and at Nālandā, the thunderbolt is preserved in the very same hand which is turned downwards whereas the gesture of threat is displayed by the hand holding the sword. As to the *aṅkuṣa*, it appears on the proper left part: used for directing the elephant, its origin should perhaps be looked for in the close character of Aparājītā. The latter did not own such an attribute but she subdued Gaṇapati and besides, when she disappeared from the cult and its artistic illustration, she made room for Mārīcī.

When the sword disappeared on the images of 11th and 12th c. which have been collected in eastern Bihar or in Bengal, the thunderbolt recovered its initial position in the upper right hand whereas the goad appeared in a right hand. Hence, we notice in the left hands the bow, the flower of *aśoka* and the noose; the fourth right hand appears in front of the breast, displaying the gesture of threat. The *pāśa* is usually held by the lower hand lying above the thigh but it can also be presented by the hand displaying the *tarjanīmudrā* (app. 33 & 35, fig. 17), which allows to free the fourth hand lying on the thigh. This hand either holds the thread, separated from the needle seen in the corresponding right hand or offers the needle (with the thread in the proper right hand then). The image from Lakhi Sarai (fig. 17) combines, moreover, the noose to the thunderbolt - with the *pāśa* behind Mārīcī, the result is an attribute named *vajrapāśa* in the *sādhana* 145.³⁶

2. Vairocana and the caitya

Like Aparājītā, Mārīcī belongs to the *kula* of Vairocana who is usually depicted in the centre of or above the tiara worn by the goddess (fig. 14).³⁵ The texts indicate that Mārīcī stands within the womb of a *caitya*, the *harmikā* of which is shown above the high-relieved arch which indicates the upper line of the monument. Two branches of the *aśoka*, the emblematic tree of the goddess, are carved on either side of the upper part of the *caitya*.³⁶ After Bodh Gayā, where it appears only rarely (app. 7), the architectural motif is integrated to the images from Nālandā (app. 21, 22, 24-26, figs. 6 & 9) or from the region although this part of the stela is very often damaged, which prevents us to make a definite observation concerning this point. In Bengal, the motif knows a privileged treatment, forming a niche in high-relief (app. 35-47, figs. 19-20).

The superposition of the monument on the tree like the mere presence of the latter require an explanation. The tree is, first of all, in the present context, the place where a Bodhisattva becomes a Buddha; and from the beginning of Buddhist art, the Buddhas of the past are referred to through the tree of their Bodhi or the *stūpa* symbolizing their *parinirvāṇa*. And, as a matter of fact, the image of Mārīcī includes both elements, the *caitya* and the tree.

The closeness is evident with the sanctuary which was built around the *aśvattha* of Bodh Gayā.

The *caitya* within which Mārīcī stands is shaped as a *stūpa*. However, the word as such does not exclusively refer to such a monument: related with the *aśoka* tree, this monument could well be only a sanctuary without any specific Buddhistic connotation, an hypothesis which would be sustained by various written sources where the word *caitya* refers to sacred trees, in contradistinction to those which are not sacred.³⁷ In the images of Mārīcī which combine the monument and the tree, the branches of the tree spread very often from the part which tops the niche, as if the trunk of the tree was integrated to the monument. It would thus seem that the development is continuous since the very first illustrations of sacred trees surrounded by a *vedikā*. The shape of the monument presently reproduces the one of the sanctuary which is common in the Buddhist world, that is the *sūpa*. But this monument is much more than a simple *caitya*, which would indicate the holiness of the tree around which it is built: it is also, and probably essentially, the *caitya* as a *stūpa* which is illustrated here, a monument which does not contain the body of the Buddha but the one of Vairocana. An image of the latter is usually inserted in the head-dress of Mārīcī but the Jina can also be seen above the goddess when he is depicted, alone or together with the other four Tathāgatas, within the architectural structure (app. 24, 40, 47: alone, 36 & 39: within the group of Jina.s). Besides, one cannot forget that the holy tree *per excellentia* was and still is in the Buddhist world the *aśvattha* at Bodh Gayā under which the Buddha obtained the Enlightenment; it is thus evidently also by comparison with this tree and its holy enclosure that one should consider the *aśoka* and its *caitya* on the images of Mārīcī.

The two images of the goddess which were discovered at Kurkihār illustrate, each of them and separately, a particular treatment of the "motif" Vairocana. In the first example, the Tathāgata does not display the gesture of teaching (fig. 5; see also fig. 6) whereas in the second example, a *caitya/stūpa* replaces him (fig. 4). The presence of the latter motif demonstrates well the equivalence between the Tathāgata and the *stūpa* as we already noticed above.³⁸ As to the first image, it indicates that Vairocana can also meditate, a function which is rarely given to him in eastern India.³⁹

The Tathāgata preserves this dominant situation on the stela at Jagdiśpur. The five Jinas are seated in a sequence of trilobate niches which rest on hexagonal pillars (fig. 13). Two *caityas* adorned with streamers stand between the side Jinas. A large umbrella protects the image, embellished with handerolles and crowned by a ring shaped like an *āmalaka* which supports the double motif of the moon crescent on which lies the solar disk, i.e. the two luminaries devoured by Rāhu who is generally depicted below Mārīcī (below).

3. Aparājītā

It has been already mentioned at various places that the images of Aparājītā and Mārīcī share elements, which would reflect a certain similarity in their respective personalities. The images of the first goddess were introduced at an earlier period than those of the latter: Aparājītā occurs (in eastern India) first at Bodh Gayā below the Buddha; only in the 8th and 9th c., independant images

of her were carved at Nālandā and in the region. Her last depiction at Nālandā, in her most common form, is probably the one noticed on the Jagdīśpur stela where she appears below the Buddha, as she used to do in the earlier phase, and trampling on Gaṇapati as she does on her independent Nālandā images. It is thus in the very two sites, which are fundamental in the history of Mārīcī, that Aparājitā was also venerated at an earlier period.

Mārīcī succeeded Aparājitā and inherited her functions since the solar goddess can also be in charge of trampling on the Obstacles which can be symbolised by the Planets. We should remember also that Mārīcī possesses, on her Nālandā images, the *aṅkuśa*, an object used to direct an elephant and Aparājitā is the goddess who subdues Gaṇapati.

4. Parṇaśabarī

As noticed shortly above, the painted depictions of Mārīcī are paired with a representation of Parṇaśabarī. Both goddesses are extremely similar on these illuminations and it would appear that in certain cases, an evident will prevailed to underline their closeness. On 86-P (fig. 26) for instance, the deity stands in the womb of a *caitya*, like Mārīcī does and her cluster of leaves does not appear. On this folio and on the other two ones (83-P, 85-P; figs. 24 & 28), she stands in a field of flames like Mārīcī. Her function is also to destroy the Death and Epidemics and to tread down under her feet the Obstacles, just like Mārīcī tramples on the Obstacles eventually symbolized by the Planets.⁴⁰

It is also the place to remind the distribution of these two goddesses and of the other fierce deities Vajravārāhī and Kurukullā on the Los Angeles book covers : the first one tramples on Bhairava and Kālarātrī or on a Preta and the second can dance on a corpse.⁴¹ Kurukullā like Mārīcī or Parṇaśabarī can stand amidst the eight Cemeteries which are symbolized in the illuminations or in sculptures through a large aura of flames. When the boards are put side by side, one observes that Vajravārāhī is depicted above Parṇaśabarī whereas Kurukullā is on the same side as Mārīcī. The four of them are perhaps distributed at the four gates of a *maṇḍala*.

Parṇaśabarī is pot-bellied, has a green complexion, is three-faced with, according to the text, a black face on the proper right side and a white face on the proper left side, a distribution of colours which is observed on fig. 26.⁴² She should hold the thunderbolt and the hatchet in the right hands, should display the gesture of threatening while holding the noose with a left hand, should also present a cluster of leaves on this side and should hold, to conclude, the bow and the arrow. Moreover, she should trample on the Obstacles or on Disease and Death : this is the iconography illustrated by 83-P or 85-P (figs. 24 & 28) (the leaves are partly flaked off and were illustrated through lines painted in gold). The cluster of leaves is not shown on 83-P (fig. 26). The text also mentions her particular dress made of leaves, this is rendered in painting through a dark blue dress covering her breast and her legs on which are painted small flower-like motifs either in yellow or white or in various colours.

The similarity between the two goddesses can eventually lead to confusion : the deity illustrated

on 84 is perhaps Mārīcī since an animal face is profiled above the right ear but on the other side, she holds a sprig of leaves which are similar to those seen on 83-P (fig. 24), which would suggest an identification with Parṇaśabarī - moreover, as on 83-P or 85-P (figs. 24 & 28), the goddess is green (like Amoghasiddhī, to whose *kula* she belongs) according to the description given by P. Pal. It is likely that in the very same manuscript, another folio must have presented a depiction of the second goddess, who would then have been similar to 83-M (fig. 23). Like on the book-cover also (85), branches of the *aśoka* tree are painted behind the monument where the deity stands.

The closeness of the two goddesses is also expressed in the "New Tibeto-Mongol Pantheon" published by Raghu Vira and Lokesh Chandra since their representation follow each other and are followed by the Pañcarakṣās. (all seven of them belong thus to the same volume 14 of the Kanjur).⁴³ There is evidently a connection between the two goddesses and the Pañcarakṣās, the Mārīcī illustrated on fig. 23 for instance carries an emblem surmounted by a jewel in a left hand, an attribute which characterizes Mahāpratisarā (without jewel), Mahāmāyūrī or Mahāsītavātī.⁴⁴ Among the "five protectresses", Sāhasramardinī shows the closest aspect which has been here studied: she appears to be the only one to be depicted, though rarely, in a standing position, she is also the one who tramples on human figures who probably symbolize the goblins from whom she preserves, and she can show fierce aspects characterized by the pot-belly, the frown, the broad face, the hair rising on ends, the three widely open eyes.⁴⁵

This image underlines the function of protectress of the Buddhist Law which Mārīcī has and which she acquired through the nature of her relation to Māra. One can surmise that this function is here enhanced to the prejudice of her symbolism of spiritual light: like the other deities, she has to protect and defend the scriptures; she presents similarly a horrific form on the left panel of the pedestal of the large Jagdīśpur image (fig. 10) as noticed above and her exclusive function is probably there to destroy Māra and his army. Mārīcī would thus combine the fire of destruction (of the evil) and the light of enlightenment (see below).

5. The light and the luminaries

We enter here into a fundamental and intricate aspect of Mārīcī's personality. The two solar and lunar luminaries have been observed topping the image of Jagdīśpur. This apical position could imply that the Buddha stands as master of the diurnal and nocturnal lights (fig. 12). In other terms, he could become master of the time.⁴⁶ But Mārīcī dominates also these two lights since certain *sādhanas* (132 & 135) locate the two astres in a pair of hands.⁴⁷ The very same motif can also crown the image of the goddess (fig. 19). By presenting the sun, she possesses the light which disperses the night and by holding the moon, she owns the light which gives light to the darkness. Moreover, according to the texts, the presence of the sun in the upper right hand and of the moon in the corresponding left hand, is related to aspects of Buddhist (and Hindu) yoga (below).

Within this context, and because he hides the luminaries, Rāhu asserts himself as an enemy and becomes as a result an aspect of Māra, i. e. he symbolizes the obscurity enjoined by the Evil to the

human world whereas Mārīcī reflects the luminous aspect of the Buddha. These antagonistic aspects of the light and the darkness are thus confronted with each other in the images of the goddess. Rāhu has relations with Māra ; he appears in the upper corners of the illustration of Māra's army on various Indian, Tibetan and Burmese paintings.⁴⁸⁾ But simultaneously, when he is related to the left sinew, it is his function of destroying the lunar light which is brought into the light, symmetric to the destructive fire of the sun that is also the one of the powerful time or *kalāgni* (below).

This information should probably be kept in mind when one considers the presence of Rāhu as holding the sun and the moon (figs. 18(?), 19-20; app. 22, 35, 37, 39-40, 43(?)-45, 47 : sun and moon are clearly seen on 39 & 47) when he is the coachman of Mārīcī's chariot according to some *sādhana*s (134, 137, 142 & 146). As a matter of fact, whereas on most images, Rāhu is to be found below the animals of the vehicle and is thus trampled by them, which underlines his purely negative function of destructor of the light in contradistinction with the reconquest of this light by the goddess above him, there exist at least two images (app. 33 & 39, fig. 17) where the Graha is depicted above the chariot. In both cases, the monstrous face arises above a wheel out of which either a *makara* or a sow jumps; in the image with the sow, the *makara* covers the rim of the wheel, acting most probably as the reins held by Rāhu. In this case also, the Graha holds the two astres which he has stolen whereas on the image from Lakhī Sarai (fig. 17), he presents with both hands the moon crescent. On this image, more probably than on the first one, it is likely that Rāhu is depicted, confused with the solar disk.

Mārīcī expresses the light which spread across the universe when Śākyamuni reached the Bodhi and which was confronted with the darkness created by Māra and his troupes before destroying it; as such also she "resides happily in the masse of rays" (*sādhana* 144).⁴⁹⁾ One of the most complex forms of the goddess tramples on the four great gods Viṣṇu, Indra, Śaṅkara and Brahmā who are, moreover, known under the name of the "four Māras" (*sādhana*s 132, 145 & 140).⁵⁰⁾ This is probably the key to the interpretation of the presence of the two representations of the goddess adorsed at the scene of the attack on the Jagdiṣpur image. This is even more likely since the terrific aspect of the deity (fig. 9) - she is six-faced and twelve-armed and stands within a cremation field or *śmāśana* - expresses the violence of the fight taking place. This representation stands at the beginning of the fight whereas the six-armed Mārīcī is located at the end of the event being shown after the panel where the defeated Māra is illustrated (fig.10). Whereas the first image illustrates the solar light bursting out with violence in the burning landscape of destruction during the fight against Māra, the second one, which is symmetric, reproduces the solar light spreading within a *caitya* at the moment of the Buddha's victory. This explains also why she should be venerated as the morning rises according to the *sādhana* 144.⁵¹⁾

Flames and solar rays are usually identical in plastic iconography. When the *caitya* is not illustrated, the edge of the slab can be underlined by a band of flames, but this motif belongs to the decorative vocabulary of the time. The craftsmen of Nālandā used at this place a very peculiar

shape of flames in order to illustrate the nimbus or the aura, having the shape of a question mark (deprived of the point) (app. 22, 30, fig. 7). On the other side, certain flames, which are isolated and can be either incised or carved in low-relief on the inner space (app. 7, 22, 25) do not have this shape : in this case, a broad flame is shown, round in its lower part and including three tongues arising out of it (app. 7 : fig.1, app. 25, 32 : fig. 15, app. 48 : fig. 21). Only very few examples of real cremation field are depicted; beside the panel of the Jagdiśpur stela (fig. 9), I only know a fragment from a small stela (fig.8) and the image from Lakhi Sarai (fig. 17).

This second form illustrated on the lower part of the Jagdiśpur image has been very often represented at Nālandā and in the region whereas the destructive aspect of the goddess which is embodied by the left panel on the same image was evoked through various elements: some flames only could be incised or carved in low-relief around the goddess or Rāhu is trampled under the chariot.

Other monstrous creatures are seen below Mārīcī : the *makara* who could, through its position, symbolise the reins with which the sows are led, the *kīrtimukha* or *kāla*, apotropaic mask which shows evident relations with the sun and which is carved above Rāhu, dominating, i.e. vanquishing him.⁵² A peculiar use of the *kīrtimukha* has been introduced on an image from south-east Bangladesh (fig. 20) : the face is carved on the *vairya* in which stands Mārīcī. It is split in two symmetric parts by the wide aperture of the monument which it adorns at mid-height, indicating the solar light of the latter. Beside the fact that this face is generalized in Hindu iconography, where it tops the image, it is also noteworthy to stress how different is its shape on the images of Mārīcī. It is always the same stela which enlightens the formal development noticed in Bihar. Below the attendant which sits at the feet of the goddess, a high-relieved *makara* is depicted, leaning on his forelegs and with a rising trunk. On the Ghosrāvān stela (fig. 14), the same face is depicted in low-relief : the legs are carved, the trunk rised but it is evident that the round shape of the face with its globulous eyes which change into horns reproduces the head of the *kīrtimukha*. And on the Nālandā image (app. 22), only the legs of the water monster have been preserved since the trunk is replaced by the flat nose of the "face of glory". It is thus neither really the *makara*, nor the *kīrtimukha* which are really illustrated, but rather a *makara* which has integrated features of the prophylactic mask which usually crowns the stela. This face could in the present context be considered to be simultaneously the *makara*, the symbol of the *nāgas* who can be used as reins and the *kīrtimukha*, not as an apotropaic face but as the creator of the solar light.⁵³ However, this monstrous face can be named *kīrtimukha* when it tops the stela or the lintel, i.e. when it essentially represents the fire or the solar light whereas it should be called *kāla* when it would represent the time (probably the wheel of the chariot, which is unique like on Sūrya's images). Now, the face which is carved below Mārīcī can combine these two aspects : on the stela from Lakhi Sarai (fig. 17), the *makara* arises out of a thick circle which I would suggest to identify with the wheel of time. As a matter of fact, Sūrya and, after him, Mārīcī master the time and lead the seven animals which symbolize the seven days of the week. Besides, by letting her chariot run over Rāhu, Mārīcī

frees the lu

This bring
presence
tops the
kīrtimukha
lowest part
darkness v

Some o
chariot of
goddess c
or by tho
the darkn
face of th
when the
god shoo
carries th
Mārīcī. a
the atten

The *kā*
ornamen
is seen a
that this
cannot,
of the p
illustrat
Gayā.⁵³
to a Bur
occurs o
and Ap
the *tha*
Avalok
reaction
two Be
named
one wi
gesture
by the
Buddh

frees the luminaries of the day and of the night from the latter's yoke.

This brings up the possibility of a new possible interpretation which could be given to Rāhu's presence below the monstrous mask. Apart from the late image from Lakhi Sarai, where Rāhu tops the *makara*, the Graha is always illustrated below the water creature, below the pseudo-*kīrtimukha*, and even below the animals of the chariot. In other words, he is rejected towards the lowest part of the image, a position which could justify to consider him here as a symbol of the darkness which he creates through his function of eclipse-maker.

Some other observations can be shortly done. As goddess of the solar light, Mārīcī mounts the chariot of Sūrya, with seven sows having usually replaced the horses. One can surmise that the goddess covered with her light the entire earth which had been darkened by the evil forces of Māra or by those of the eclipse-maker Rāhu and that she somehow extracted this terrestrial universe from the darkness such as Varāha rescued the earth-goddess Bhūdevī from the depth of the ocean. The face of the *makara* was perhaps also retained after this monster had become the *vāhana* of Māra when the latter had integrated the personality of Kāma. Various panels from Pāhārpur represent the god shooting his arrows, while standing on a chariot shaped as a *makara*.⁵⁴ The very same chariot carries the god on 12th c. images from south-east Bangladesh.⁵⁵ And in the description of the white Mārīcī, a rather complex form which has already been mentioned above (*sādhanas* 132 & 135), the attending figure in front of her stands above a *makara*.⁵⁶

The *kīrtimukha* and its complex symbolism was, from the 12th c. and onwards, preserved as ornament of the cushion on which the Buddha sits at his Enlightenment. On these images, the face is seen amidst volutes which cover this cushion lying above the lotus; this might perhaps indicate that this face shares the nature of the one seen above it, even that it is confused with it. One cannot, therefore, exclude the possibility that the *kīrtimukha* stands here as an allegoric illustration of the power of word and light of the Buddha, a power which found its greatest and most perfect illustration at Bodh Gayā. This motif occurs on a bronze found at Fatehpur, in the district of Gayā.⁵⁷ It is also seen on a bronze dated in the 12th or 13th c. which has been variously attributed to a Burmese or to a Tibetan artist, and on the later Tibetan copy of this bronze image.⁵⁸ To end, it occurs on a painting from Khara Khoto⁵⁹ where the pair noticed at Bodh Gayā showing Vasudhārā and Aparājītā is also painted. A further iconographic feature is present on these two bronzes and on the *thaika*, i.e. in each image, *Simhanāḍa* Lokeśvara sits below the Buddha. What is this form of Avalokiteśvara with the "roaring of the lion"?⁶⁰ It would appear at Bodh Gayā in the 11th c. as a reaction to the similar image of Mañjūsī seated on the lion.⁶¹ Beside their common vehicle, the two Bodhisattvas are related to the Buddhist word and receive accordingly titles: Mañjūsī is named Vādirāj, "the king of the disputants" or, after the name of Avalokiteśvara, *Simhanāḍa*, "the one with the roar of the lion".⁶² Through this way, we return to Vairocana whose most frequent gesture in India at that period is the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*⁶³ and whose throne is adorned by the lions of the *simhāsana*.⁶⁴ Vairocana is "the one who irradiates" the light belonging to the Buddhist word;⁶⁵ illustrating the psychic light of the Illumination, Mārīcī represents also the word

which arose from the Enlightenment and which was spoken by the Buddha in his *dharmakāya*, i.e. in his form as Vairocana.

Mārīcī is a deity who arose out of Buddhist esoterism and not from popular belief. Her similarities with Sūrya are limited to formal elements, i.e. the number of the animals, seven, pulling the chariot and on early images, the horses in place of the sows, or the position of the goddess which she shares with the bow-women who accompany the god, either in *alīḍhāsana* or in *pratyalīḍhāsana*, or the presence of the bow and the arrows which are the attributes of these archers (but the latter shoot their weapons, not Mārīcī).

However, it is evident that the goddess reveals a nature which is not only solar but fundamentally luminous. She should not be considered as a female and Buddhist copy of the Hindu god Sūrya. Mārīcī is much more than that. Her name "Rays of Light" is not to be essentially related to the god and his nature but rather to certain speculations of Buddhism about the Enlightenment on the one hand, about the light which arose at that very moment on the other hand. One is forced to refer to texts like the *Guhyasamājatantra* or the *Pañcakrama* to trace certain elements which belong to the personality of the deity.⁶⁶ The second text includes a precious passage for our concern, which is here quoted in the translation given by Alex Wayman :⁶⁷

" 'Light' is the (moon-rise) part of night. The day with its spreading rays of the bright sun is 'Spread-of-Light'. Twilight is 'Culmination-of-Light'." (*āloko rātribhāgaḥ sphuṭaravikiraṇaḥ syād aivālokābhāsaḥ saṃdhyālokopalabhaḥ prakṛtibhir asakṛd yujyate svābhir etat*).

This system of the three Lights is hierarchical since one glides from the light of the night, *āloka* ("light") to the one of the day, *ālokābhāsa* ("manifestation of light") and to reach the light of dusk, *ālokapalabdhi* ("intuition of light"); it is also the subject of numerous analogies which can be shortly summed up :

āloka : light which is assimilated to the left (*vāma*), the moon (*candra*) and the night, to the lotus (*padma*) and the woman (*strī*), to knowledge (*prajñā*) and emptiness (*śūnya*), to Rāhu, to the *sambhogakāya*;

ālokābhāsa : light which is assimilated to the right (*dakṣiṇa*), the sun (*sūrya*) and the day, to the thunderbolt (*vajra*) and the man, to the means (*upāya*), to extreme emptiness (*atīśūnya*), to the fire of time (*kālagñi*), to the *nirmanakāya*.⁶⁸

This is the "mystic physiology" of the yoga as it was called by Mircea Eliade.⁶⁹ The two states of light are related to the two nerves running on either side of the central sinew (*avadhūti*) which can be also identified with the *dharmakāya*. Beside, the opponants converge towards each other and from the fusion of the two lights or more precisely of the *upāya* and the *prajñā*, the Enlightenment arises also named then *prajñopāya*,⁷⁰ *ālokapalabdhi*,⁷¹ or even *mahāśūnya*⁷² which is the place of transition towards the absolute Emptiness or *sarvaśūnya*.⁷³ It is perhaps within this context that one should consider the information included in the *sādhana* 144 which stipulates that the *upāya* and the *prajñā* are both present below Mārīcī. In this position, and in couple, they are placed on the central axis of the image (either literary or plastic) where they merge.

One has recognized, by passing, various elements which occur in the iconography of Mārīcī. First, the two astres, sun and moon, which various *sādhanas* (132 & 135) locate in the upper hands of the deity and which we first related to the passing of time. Without completely dropping this hypothesis, it is required to inflect it since it is also the Light in its successive levels, opposed but complementary, which is here depicted. This opposition/complementarity of the two parts is also noticed in the presence of the thunderbolt, male symbol, in a proper right hand, and of a flower in a proper left hand - the text mentions of course the *padma* as female repository of the *vajra* but the *śoka* attributed to Mārīcī by the *sādhanas* is fundamentally related to femininity.

Mārīcī is thus placed in a highly speculative context. Her first representations are located at Bodh Gayā, but very few elements distinguish them from the later images; no literary description is available for them. It seems therefore that from the very beginning, the image of the deity shows her standard form.

When Mārīcī appears in the Buddhist world of Bodh Gayā, Aparājītā escapes from it. The representations of the latter are always integrated in the lower part of the image of the Buddha at his Enlightenment and only the ateliers at Nālandā decided to represent her as the main subject of their images. The images of Aparājītā do not generally appear after the 9th c. whereas those of Mārīcī are from then and onwards the object of an increasing worship in this site and the region around it. It is thus probable that in a certain way, the obedience paid to a deity succeeded to the one offered to the other one : in the devotion, the cult of Mārīcī followed the one of Aparājītā. It is evident that the personality of the first one is richer than the one of the second one whose fundamental function is to lock the forces of evil which are symbolized by Gaṇapati or the Navagrahas. The *Vairocanābhisambodhitānta*, which was probably composed in Maharashtra in the 6th and 7th c.⁷⁵ prescribes to represent "in the lower area of the Mantra Lord (= Śākyamuni) ... the Mahākrodha called Aparājīta and the goddess Aparājītā; also Kṣīpātī (field protector) holding in hand a pot."⁷⁶

If Kṣīpātī evokes Bhūdevī who is also called at the time of the Enlightenment by Śākyamuni, one finds also here the goddess who attended to the event and one of the Great Krodha who is more often known as Prajñāntaka.⁷⁶ And we should shortly remind that another Great Krodha, Yamāntaka, was also summoned by the future Buddha at the eve of the Enlightenment according to the *Kṛṣṇayamārikalpa*.⁷⁷ This instant of perfect wisdom is thus surrounded by characters who are active in the fight against the material forces symbolized by Māra and his armies.

Mārīcī is inserted in this schema, being one of these "deities" who have to defend the Buddhist Law but she does not only integrate this very active position which is illustrated by the functions endowed to her attributes in the literary sources or in the illuminations, she does also represent the infinite brightness which, at the moment of the victory or of the domination of the forces of evil, impregnates the universe. In this perspective, she assumes a double position at the level of the *dharmakāya*, where she arises out of Vairocana, the Tathāgata of the centre which is pure light, and at the level of the *sambhogakāya* where Śākyamuni reaches the Bodhi when the irradiating

Vairocana penetrates him. It is here the place to remind that the *sādhana* 144 locates Mārīcī at the double level of the *dharmā*^o and of the *samboghakāya*. The goddess is thus a place of passage between Vairocana, the "Illuminator" and Śākyamuni; she entertains with the first one extremely close ties as testified in the *Mahāvairocanasūtra/Vairocanābhisambodhitāntra* which locates Vairocana at the two *kāyas* mentioned in the *sādhana* 144.⁷⁸ She is the brightness of the one transmuted in the other one, she is the light flashing when the *prajñā* hurts the heart and opens the mind to the Enlightenment (and at Nālandā, let us remember, she is armed with the sword and the thunderbolt).⁷⁹ The appearance of this image proceeds thus from the evolution of the imagery related to the Bodhi but reflects also the speculations bearing on the Light inherent in the Enlightenment.

Appendix : Images of Mārīcī

A. Bodh Gayā

1. Mahant's Compound. Publ.: Leoshko 1987, fig. 167 & pp. 308-309; Bautze-Pieron 1989a, p. 276 No. 19 where 19th c. sources are quoted, which published this image (today hidden behind a curtain).
2. Mahant's Compound. Publ.: Leoshko 1987, fig. 169 & p. 309; Leoshko 1991, fig. 4.
3. Bodhi garden, fragment. Publ.: Leoshko 1987, fig. 166 & p. 308.
4. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Inscription (in Chinese) dated in A.D. 1021. Publ.: Beal 1881, pp. 554-556 & pl.; Cunningham 1892, pl. XXX-1 & pp. 69-71; Behrsing 1943, No. 23; S. Huntington 1984, fig. 83 & pp. 78, 246-249; Leoshko 1987, fig. 12 & 172 and pp. 47-49 & 311-312; Leoshko 1988, fig. 17; Leoshko 1991, fig. 5; M.Mitra 1998, pp. 346-347, photo 45.
5. Present whereabouts unknown. Upper part of a slab which was incised with an inscription in Chinese, similar to the one listed above (No.4). The Buddha sits in the central niche, displaying the gesture of Enlightenment whereas Mārīcī is depicted in the right niche (the left niche is lost). Publ.: Cunningham 1892, pl. XXX-5 & p. 74.
6. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Imprint. Publ.: Anderson 1883, p. 60 cat. B.G.137; Harle 1977, pl. 5-d; Leoshko 1987, fig. 171 & p. 310.
7. Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin inv. I 380. Publ.: besides Bautze-Pieron 1989a, p. 276, No. 20 (with places of publications before 1989), see Behrsing 1943, No. 21. Leoshko 1995, fig. 9 & Bautze-Pieron 1998a, cat. 7, p. 22 (with references to further publications). *Fig. 1.*
8. Patna Museum, 16 cm. Publ.: Gupta 1965 cat. 65; Saraswati 1977, ill. 128 (the exact find-spot is unknown and Saraswati locates it, without any argument, at Nālandā; but, from a stylistic and an iconographic point of view, this image is much closer to stelae produced at Bodh Gayā).
9. Indian Museum, Calcutta, 22 cm. Publ.: Bloch 1911, p. 69 cat. 6267 (the find-spot is not mentioned); Banerji 1933, pl. XII-b; Saraswati 1977, ill. 126 (origin located at Nālandā but the author systematically attributes to this site any image of the goddess which he publishes!); Mallmann 1986, p. 264; M.Mitra 1998, pp. 344-345, photo:43.
10. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Publ.: Banerji 1933, pl. XLII-b & p. 98; D.C. Bhattacharyya 1978, fig. 7; the

same 1979/1
such as the g

Gayā).

11. The Rus

12. Museum

style). Pu

B. Itkhauri

13. Bhadrak

C. Kurkiha

14. Asian A

d'Argenc

Bartholo

(with fur

15. Luckne

Vogel 19

fig. 485

D. Hasra

16. Image

author, the

nothing is

E. Nālandā

17. Nation

18. Nālan

19. Nālan

20. Nālan

21. Nālan

not reman

22. The E

publicatio

23. Nālan

24. India

(right s

Sarasw

M.Mit

25. In si

1977,

variou

same 1979/1980, fig. 27; M.Mitra 1998, pp.345-346, photo 44 (no precise find-spot is known but elements such as the girdle on the thighs, Rāhu in the centre of the pedestal are typical of the images from Bodh Gayā).

11. The Russek collection, Zürich, 81 cm (Bodh Gayā/Kurkihār style), **Fig. 2.**

12. Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin inv. IC 34751, 24 cm, fragment (missing since 1945) (Bodh Gayā style). Publ.: Behring 1943, No. 32 & fig. 6 p. 13, Bautze-Pieron 1998a, cat. 66, p. 40.

B. Itkhauri

13. Bhadrakālī Mandir, 46 x 29 cm (related to the atelier of Bodh Gayā), **Fig. 3.**

C. Kurkihār

14. Asian Art Museum of San Francisco, The Avery Brundage collection, 74 cm. Publ.: Lefebvre d'Argencé-Tse 1969, cat. 32; Pāla-Sena Sculpture 1984, cat. 8; Mallmann 1986, p. 264 & note 4; Tse Bartholomew 1989, fig. 7; Huntington-Huntington 1989, fig. 5 and the same 1990, cat. 12 & pp. 135-136 (with further places of publication mentioned); Bautze-Pieron 1995a, fig. 3 (Kurkihār style), **Fig. 4.**

15. Lucknow Museum, 72 cm. Publ.: Cunningham 1892, pl. XXX-4; Vogel 1903-04, pl. LXII, fig. 4; Vogel 1932, fig. 38; Kirfel 1948, fig. 48; B. Bhattacharyya 1958, fig. 154; Smith 1969, pl. 98-A: *Chhavi*, fig. 485, **Fig. 5.**

D. Hasra Kol

16. Image seen in a local temple by Keith 1910, fig. 9 & p. 64. According to the drawing given by this author, the goddess would have two animal faces but it is clear that the proper right head is the sow, nothing is certain concerning the left one which has been drawn as being a lion (!).

E. Nālandā

17. National Museum, New Delhi. Publ.: Banerji 1933, pl. XLII-c; Saraswati 1977, fig. 123.

18. Nālandā Museum, **Fig. 6.**

19. Nālandā Museum, Publ.: Saraswati 1977, ill. 127.

20. Nālandā Museum, **Fig. 7.**

21. Nālandā Museum, Publ.: Saraswati 1977, ill. 124 & 125 (twice the same sculpture but the author does not remark it).

22. The British Museum, London. Publ.: Bautze-Pieron 1989a, p. 283 No. 53 (with previous places of publication) & fig. 19.

23. Nālandā Museum, **Fig. 8.**

24. Indian Museum, Calcutta, 115 cm. Publ.: Broadley 1872, pp. 18-19 No. LVI; Burgess 1897, pl. 230 (right side) or Asher 1970, pl. VII; Foucher 1900, fig. 27 p. 149; B. Bhattacharyya 1958, fig. 153; Saraswati 1977, ill. 120; *Tantrische Kunst des Buddhismus*, p. 128 cat. 24; Leoshko 1987, fig. 165; M.Mitra 1998, pp.347-350, photo 46..

25. In situ, east from site 14. Publ.: Goetz 1966, pl. 213; Sankalia 1972, fig. 6; Sahai 1975, fig. 44; Saraswati 1977, ill. 122; Paul 1995, pl. 47 (wrong find-spot but this work includes a number of wrong attributions, various images said to be from Nālandā, have, as a matter of fact, a different origin, see Bautze-Pieron

1989b).

26. Jagdišpur/Nālandā. Approximately 30 cm h. Mentioned by Leoshko 1993/94, p. 252. **Fig. 10.**
 27. Jagdišpur/Nālandā. Publ.: Leoshko 1993/94, fig. 6 (unidentified). **Fig. 9.**
 28. Present whereabouts unknown (Nālandā style). Publ.: Sotheby's New York 5.12.1992, # 315.
 29. Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin inv. I 549, fragment (Nālandā style). 17 cm. Publ.: Behrsing 1943, No. 65 & fig. 9, p. 22; Bautze-Picron 1998, cat. 67, p. 40.
 30. Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin inv. I 1131, fragment (Nālandā style). 21 cm. Publ.: Bautze-Picron 1998, cat. 68, pp. 40-41.

F. Ghosrāvān and Tetrāvān

31. Ghosrāvān. **Fig. 14.**
 32. Tetrāvān. **Fig. 15.**

G. Lakhi Sarai and Uren

33. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Publ.: Bautze-Picron 1991/92, fig. 20 & p. 257 No. A,22 where previous places of publication are mentioned. Add to it: Bhattacharyya 1964, pl. IX and M.Mitra 1998, pp.350-351, photo 47. **Fig. 17.**
 34. Uren. Present whereabouts unknown. Publ.: Bautze-Picron 1991/92, fig.41 (*Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey, Eastern Circle, for 1907-1908*, photo 94).

H. North Bengal

35. Sarakhanda, district of West Dinajpur. State Archaeological Museum of West Bengal, Calcutta, 77 cm. Publ.: Das Gupta 1963, fig. 22; Sengupta 1991, pl. 16; M.Mitra 1998, pp.353-354, figs.38-39. **Fig. 18.**
 36. Narikelbaria, district of Rajshahi. Varendra Research Museum, Rajshahi. Publ.: Basak-Bhattacharyya 1919, p. 6 cat. A(d)1/141; Saraswati 1977, ill. 121; Sengupta 1993, pl. 69.
 37. Probably from north Bengal (it illustrates the compact style of the region, where empty spaces are rarely reserved, where motifs are accumulated, see e.g. the superimposition of the motifs from the goddess herself downwards to the bust of Rāhu at the bottom, or the devotee who is partly hidden by the female attendant on the proper right side of Mārīcī). Staatliches Museum für Völkerkunde, München, inv. L. 115. Publ.: Mallebrein 1984, pp. 46-47, *Mare Erythaeum* 1998, cat. 24 p. 32 (with further references).
 38. Mahasthangarh Museum. From Mahadepur, district of Rajshahi. Fragment.

I. South Bengal

39. Vikrampur, district of Dhaka. Varendra Research Museum, Rajshahi. Publ.: Basak-Bhattacharyya 1919, p. 6 cat. A(d)2/137 and first unnumbered plate at the end of the book; Bhattasali 1929, p. 44 cat. [2]; Saraswati 1977, ill. 118; Sengupta 1993, pl. 68.
 40. Vikrampur, district of Dhaka. Varendra Research Museum, Rajshahi. Publ.: Basak-Bhattacharyya 1919, p. 6 cat. A(d)3/94; Bhattasali 1929, p. 45; Saraswati 1977, ill. 230.
 41. Panditsār, district of Faridpur. Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka. 130 cm. Publ.: Bhattasali 1929, pl. XIV & pp. 43-44; Dani 1959, ill. 35; Saraswati 1977, ill. 117; Huntington 1984, fig. 213; Sengupta 1993, pl. 67.

42. Ujani, district of Kirfel 1948.
 43. Mainamat
 44. Mainamat
Buddha 1967.
 45. Mainamat
 46. (Probably
 cm. Publ.:
 47. From sou
 and for the
 region, wh
 collection,
 48. Bhavanip
 been often
 note 158 w
 list, add M
 however, i
 presented p

J. Bronzes

49. Found in
 pl. XXXV
 1981, pl. 3
 50. From Pa
 51. G. Heil
 52. Present

K. Stone sc

53. Sarnāth.
 Saraswati
 54. Present
 23 where
 55. Salihun
 XXVII-X
 Murthy I
 mentioni
 included
 56. Sonepu
 57. Kendra
 1998, pp
 58. Ayodh

42. Ujani, district of Faridpur. Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka. 76 cm. Publ.: Bhattasali 1929, p. 44; Kirfel 1948, fig. 49; Majumdar 1971, fig. 65; Dani 1959, ill. 43; Saraswati 1977, ill. 116.
43. Mainamati, Salban vihāra. Publ.: Sengupta 1993, pl. 27.
44. Mainamati. Mainamati Museum. 101 cm. Publ.: *5000 Jahre* 1962, cat. 346 & 48th (unnumbered) pl.; *Buddha* 1967, p. 40.
45. Mainamati. Mainamati Museum. c. 60 cm. **Fig. 19.**
46. (Probably from the region of) Mainamati (compare to 42-44). Los Angeles County Museum of Art. 36.9 cm. Publ.: Pal 1988, pp. 191-192, cat. 91.
47. From south east Bangladesh (compare for the large arch and the very clearly depicted *caitya* with 40-45 and for the distribution of the attendants, with 43; it shows moreover the linear style which is typical of the region, where large empty spaces are preserved around the elements which are very clearly drawn). Private collection, Basel. 94 cm. Publ.: Bautze-Pieron 1992b, fig. 3; Sotheby's London 24.4.1990, # 94. **Fig. 20.**
48. Bhavanipur, district of Dhaka. National Museum of Bangladesh, Dhaka. 137 cm. Publ.: this image has been often published, identified either with Mahāpratisarā or with Bhṛkuṭī, see Mevissen 1991/92, p. 373 note 158 where the references are provided with, including the various proposed identifications. To his list, add Mallmann 1986, p. 295 who mentions the image in her chapter on the Pañcarakṣās. Mevissen, however, in his detailed study of these goddesses, doubts about this identification; his arguments are presented p. 359 of his article ("the identification as M. . . is not without doubt. . ."). **Fig. 21., Figs. 21-a, b.**

J. Bronzes from Bihar/Bengal

49. Found in the district of Patna. Indian Museum, Calcutta, inv. N.S.4248. Publ.: *AR of the ASI 1923-24*, pl. XXXVI-c and pp. 101 & 232; Sinha 1958, fig. 112; Mitra ed. 1979, fig. 127 & p. 97; Bandyopadhyaya 1981, pl. 32; Schroeder 1981, ill. 68c; Ray & alii 1986, pl. 203; Paul 1995, pl. 68.
50. From Pabna. Bangladesh National Museum, inv. 77, 1714.
51. G. Heil collection, Berlin. 18 x 11 x 6 cm. Publ.: Sotheby's New York 20.3.1997, # 282. **Fig. 16.**
52. Present whereabouts unknown (collection Bonardi, Roma). Publ.: Tucci 1973, pl. 143.

K. Stone sculptures from Orissa and other regions

53. Sārnāth, Uttar Pradesh. Publ.: Sahnī 1972, pp. 148-149 (with supplementary references) & pl. XVII-b; Saraswati 1977, ill. 129.
54. Present whereabouts unknown. Probably from Uttar Pradesh. Publ.: Sotheby's New York 5.10.1990, # 23 where other places of publication are listed.
55. Salihundam, Andhra Pradesh. Publ.: *AR of the ASI 1919-20*, pl. XXIII-a; R. Subrahmanyam 1964, pl. XXVII-XXVIII B & pp. 93-94; D.C. Bhattacharyya 1974, pl. II & p. 19; the same 1978, fig. 8; K. Krishna Murthy 1989, pl. 10-12 & pp. 35-37 (this author reproduces the text of Subrahmanyam without even mentioning the latter, and this remark can be applied to every description of the images from Salihundam included in Krishna Murthy's book !).
56. Sonapur, Patna Museum. Publ.: D.C. Bhattacharyya 1979/1980, fig. 26.
57. Kendrapārā. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Publ.: Sahu 1958, fig. 40; Mohapatra 1986, II, p. 56; M. Mitra 1998, pp. 351-352, photo 48.
58. Ayodhyā. Publ.: Vasu 1911, pl. 49; Sahu 1958, fig. 64 & pp. 209-210 (a right arm is broken since

- Vasu's publication); Mohapatra 1986, II, fig. 71.
59. Khiching, Bāripadā Museum. Publ.: *AR of the ASI 1922-23*, pl. XLI-f; Chanda 1929, pl. V-a; Sahu 1958, fig. 71 & p. 214; Mohapatra 1986, II, fig. 71.
60. Aṣṭaraṅga, valley of Prāchī. Publ.: Sahu 1958, fig. 74 & pp. 217-218.
61. Udlā, Bāripadā Museum. Publ.: Sahu 1958, fig. 79 & p. 222.
62. Udlā, Bāripadā Museum. Publ.: Sahu 1958, p. 222.
- 63-80, Ratnagiri. The goddess is depicted in the niche of 16 *caityas*. Debala Mitra sums up in her report the various forms which are illustrated (1981, I, pp. 131-134), classifying them according to the number of arms and faces. We can presently ignore the three depictions of Aśokakāntā (p. 134) and only keep the victorious form of the goddess. She is shown as such six times with three human faces and mounting a chariot pulled by horses (images 63-68)(pp. 131-132, pl. LXXVII-C & D, LXXVIII-A), four times with a face of sow and eventually standing on a chariot pulled by sows (images 69-72)(pl. LXXVI-C & D, LXXVII-A & B). Beside these ten images, we find only one depiction of the goddess with three faces and eight arms (image 73)(pl. LXXVIII-B). To end, two examples are known of a seated Mārīcī with only one face and six arms, above the sows (images 74-75)(pl. LXXVIII-C & D).

Besides, we find five fragments of drums from votive *caityas* where Mārīcī is depicted (pp. 107-108). Two groups can be distinguished, in the first one, the goddess has three human faces and her chariot is pulled by horses (images 76-77)(pl. LIV-A & B), in the second one, she has a face of sow and sows pull her chariot (images 78-80)(pl. LI-B, LIV-C & D).

L. Manuscript illuminations and book-covers

(including the depictions of Mārīcī[M] & Parīśabarī[P])

81. Varendra Research Museum, Rajshahi, folio 91 recto. Publ.: Bautze-Picron 1999, fig. 41.
82. Vredenburg Manuscript, Victoria and Albert Museum inv. I.S.4-10/1958, folio 90, central illumination, Rāmapāla's regnal year 36 (beginning of the 12th c.). Publ.: Losty 1990, fig. 6 & p. 193. **Fig. 22.**
83. Vredenburg Manuscript, Victoria and Albert Museum inv. I.S.4-10, 1958, folio 179, left illumination (M), folio 179, right illumination (P). Publ.: Losty 1990, figs. 8 & 10, pp. 194-195; Zwalf 1985, cat. 157 p. 116 & ill. p. 110. (On either side of Vasudhārā). **Figs. 23 & 24.**
84. Los Angeles County Museum of Art inv. M.79.9.9a, Madanapāla's reign, year 17 (A.D. 1160). Publ.: Pal 1993, cat. 7 pp. 66-67.
85. Los Angeles County Museum of Art inv. M.77.19.2b (book-cover, respectively third illumination from the left (M) and right (P) sides). 12th c. Publ.: Pal 1993, cat. 9 pp. 71-72. **Figs. 27 & 28.**
86. British Library inv. Or. MS 13940, folios 43 recto (M) & 41 verso (P), South-east Bengal (as opposed to Losty: western Bengal), c. A.D. 1100-1125. Publ.: Losty 1989, figs. 57 & 60 and p. 17, Losty 1982, cat. 10 p. 34 (with ill. of P). **Figs. 25 & 26.**
87. Cambridge, University Library inv. Add.1643, folio 200, Nepal, D. 1015. Publ.: Foucher 1900, pl. VIII-6 & p. 201, Saraswati 1977, ill. 257 & p. LXXXIX (together with a depiction of Vasudhārā on the same side of the folio, see Foucher 1900, 201).
88. Asiatic Society of Calcutta inv. A.15, folio 148(?), Nepal, A.D. 1071. Publ.: Foucher 1900, p. 212 No.

26. Saraswati 1977, pl. 258 & pp. LXXXIX-XCI.
89. Cambridge, University Library inv. Add.1688, folio 45. Regnal year 14 of Nayapāla (middle of 11th c.). Publ.: Foucher 1900, pl. IX-6 & p. 150 ("çakti"), Saraswati 1977, ill. 206. Saraswati 1978, p. 41.
90. Royal Asiatic Society, London. Nālandā, regnal year 4 of Govindapāla (P). Publ.: Saraswati 1978, p. 89 (see also Losty 1982, cat. 9 pp. 33-34). Only P: apparently M is not included in the manuscript (letter by J.P. Losty, dated 29.9.1998).
91. Asiatic Society of Bombay inv. 210, folio 222 verso, central illumination. Regnal year 39 of Govindapāla. Publ.: Gorakshkar/Desai 1987, pl. X-a & p. 563.

Notes

- 1) I would like to thank Gert Mevissen for having read this paper and made various suggestions (and corrections!). This paper belongs to a larger research dealing with the iconography of the Enlightenment, various aspects of which have already been published in Bautze-Pieron 1995/96, 1996 and 1998h.
- 2) The most famous is the stela of Jagdiśpur, located south-west of the archaeological site of Nālandā; it was in particular published by John C. Huntington in 1987. Other stelae reproducing in a detailed manner this iconographic topic were carved in south-east Bangladesh (Bautze-Pieron 1992a). Detailed photos of these images and from the Jagdiśpur one were published recently in the two papers mentioned in the previous note (1995/96, figs. 22-23; 1996, figs. 13-16). The subject is also illustrated on an image kept in the temple of Ghosṭāyān or on slabs from votive *caitya*s from Bodh Gaya (Bautze-Pieron 1995/96, fig. 12a & p. 383, note 6).
- 3) Bautze-Pieron 1995/96, pp. 372-376 discusses some of these "deities".
- 4) Information and quotation from Yi-Liang 1945, p.244. For instance, a painted *mandala* from China, dated 1717, which is "most likely based on the *Marīci Bodhisatva Sutra* that was translated during the Song period (960-1279)" (Patry Leidy/Thurman 1998, cat. 48 & detail photograph p. 112) or a gilt-bronze which shows the goddess on a chariot drawn by nine sows (Sotheby's London, 26.11.1984, # 72). U. von Schroeder 1981, fig. 138E & 155F reproduces also various late images of the deity and another most interesting gilt copper image is quoted below in note 47 where the eight-armed deity stands within the womb of the *caitya*. Four images of the goddess are painted on the walls and one is carved within a *stūpa* of the chapel located in the southern part of the first level of the *caitya* at Gyantse (15th c.) (Ricca/Lo Bue 1993, pp. 101-102 & 227, pls. 87-89), but all those representations illustrate how specific texts can be transcribed in pictural or sculptural, i.e. visual, words and do not partake, like the earlier images from India, of the elaboration of a particular iconographical type. Also the descriptions of Japanese images given by Frédéric (1992, pp. 226-227) are related to Indian prototypes; there also, she can, for instance, wear in her head-dress either an image of Mahāvairocana or a representation of the *caitya* (like on the images at Kurkihār). A Tibetan xylograph reproduced by Grünwedel (1900, fig. 118), illustrates the iconographic current of Bodh Gayā and Kurkihār, where the goddess is six-handed and presents the very same attributes.
- 5) Foucher 1905, pp. 91-99, B. Bhattacharyya 1924 & 1958; although only the 1958 edition is nowadays referred to (pp. 207-209, 210-214), one should mention the early date of the first edition of this work which broke new ground as well as Foucher's book. Bh. Sahai 1975, pp. 243-252. R.O. Meisezahl 1965-66 & Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann 1969 and from the same 1986 (reprint of 1976), pp. 259-265. See also Bhattacharyya 1964 (first published in 1932), pp. 136-139 which is a summary of the information included in 1924/1958.
- 6) D.C. Bhattacharyya 1978, pp. 18-22. But in a rather unconvincing manner: on the one hand, the author quotes, p. 19, the *Śīlparama*, of a late date, the 16th c., as he admits himself (p. 20), but according to him, the textual passages which he takes into consideration belong to the oldest substratum of the text (!). On the other hand, he makes use of names which are **nowadays** given by worshippers to images of Marīci in Orissa (an idea which he also introduces in his work of 1979/1980, p. 65). But, today, these images are venerated in a completely non-Buddhist context and examples are numerous, in Bihar for instance, where Buddhist images are worshipped as if being Hindu, the large Buddha at Jagdiśpur is named Rukminī, e.g. As to the mentioning of the Siddhas which the author makes, pp. 21 & 10 note 22, it betrays an evident misunderstanding of the writings left by these ascetics, which are too far from the *sādhana* literature to suggest any link between the two. It is an evidence that the plastic Buddhist iconography is canonical inasmuch as it arises within a monastic surrounding where it developed parallel to the literary iconography of the *sādhana*s. And the Siddhas were essentially anchorites. In his work of 1979/1980, pp. 18 & 34, he evokes the transfer of Śū

rya's vehicle to Mārīcī and underlines that the latter represents (in his eyes) "the concept of the combination of the Sun-god and the Devī..."

Another but similar approach has been recently exposed by Rajendra Ram (1990-1992): he considers the image of the goddess as being part of a practically social revolution which the Buddhists were aiming at, by sustaining the Untouchables and criticizing the Hindu social structure ("Pigs of the chariot ... show an extraordinary approach of the Buddhist artists and priests to untouchables and down trodden castes of Indian society", p. 235). The author speaks of a "socio-religious renaissance under the guidance of the Vajrayāna Buddhism" (pp. 235-236), considers the 84 Siddhas as "formidable unconventional messengers of social change" (p. 236), writes that "art is in fact for social use" (id.), argues that there exists "a material truth behind appreciation of art motifs depicted in specific socio-religious perspective" (pp. 236-237) but at the end does not show the specificity of the goddess's images with respect to his theory. I doubt that the "down trodden castes" could find themselves in so complex images as those of Mārīcī or of any other deity of the late Buddhist pantheon in India; this does not mean that elements of this world of images could not trace their formulation in the social surrounding, but this can also be argued about "Hindu" imagery, some images of Śiva or of the Goddess, e.g. Cāmuṇḍā, do not particularly seem to fit within the "Hindu social" order which R. Ram evokes.

- 7) Leoshko 1991, pp. 232-233 in an extension of her Ph.D. published in 1987 (where the iconography is dealt with on pp. 306-313).
- 8) In one of her last articles, in 1991, Mireille Bénisti wrongly concluded that this *mūdrā* was never attributed to Vairocana in India. But, in the Shingon, which traces most probably its origin in Maharashtra (Wayman/Tajima 1992), two gestures are traditionally shown by this supreme Buddha, i.e. the gesture of meditation and the *bodhiyagjīnūdrā* known in Gandhāra and rarely encountered in the Peninsula where it is replaced by the gesture of teaching. As it was already demonstrated by John C. Huntington in his study of the caves 6 & 7 at Aurangabad (1981), Vairocana is represented in India displaying the one and the other *mūdrā*s; see also Bautze-Picron [in the press] concerning the images of the Jina at Nasik.
- 9) The paper by John C. Huntington 1987 deals with this image. The central scene of the pedestal is also reproduced by Bautze-Picron 1995/96, fig. 23 & the Bodhisattvas are illustrated in Bautze-Picron 1997, figs.20-21. Concerning the fragment which is preserved in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, see Bautze-Picron 1989a, pp. 281 & 287 No. 45 & fig. 13.
- 10) Mallmann 1986, pp. 262-263 & B. Bhattacharyya 1968, vol. I, pp. 286-288 & 296.
- 11) Mallmann 1986, pp. 14 & 425 (in the plastic iconography).
- 12) MacDonald 1962, pp. 117 & 118 and note 6; Mallmann 1986, pp. 434-435 & Wayman 1992, p. 126.
- 13) See Bautze-Picron 1995/96 pp. 372-373, particularly note 85.
- 14) Above note 11 & Mallmann 1986, p. 449 (in plastic iconography). We should also mention the presence of a goddess with a sow's head at the side of the green Tārā on the Ford painting (often published, see e.g. Huntington/Huntington 1990, cat. 108 pp. 318-320 with further references, see also the remarks in Bautze-Picron 1993, pp. 290-292). Interesting enough, the goddess, who is not named, is seen behind Aśaokantā Mārīcī. This painting is related to a *sādhana* written in the 7th c. by Candragomin as Eva Allinger 1997 has recently shown (see her pp. 667-669 for the information contained in the text and the comparison with the painting). The knife and the skull are held on the painting and in the *sādhana* by the dark Bhṛkuṭī seen on the proper left side of the Tārā.
- 15) Concerning the diverging opinions, consult Mevissen 1991/92, p. 373 note 158 and here appendix No. 48.
- 16) *Sādhana*s 132, 134 to 143, 145 & 146 introduce the head of sow but not the *sādhana*s 133 & 144 (the numerotation is given after B. Bhattacharyya's edition of the *Sādhana*malā in 1968, vol. I, pp. 274-306). Texts evoke the head without discrimination of *vārahāmkhā* or of *sākaramukhī*.
- 17) Mallmann 1986, pp. 31 & 261.
- 18) Mallmann 1986, p. 261.
- 19) It is indeed not the *trīśūla* which various scholars recognized here (app. 48); see also Mallmann 1986, p. 262.
- 20) Mallmann 1986, p. 291 & note 5 (Pañcarakṣā) and p. 262 (Mārīcī, *sādhana* 145).
- 21) Always in *sādhana* 144. Concerning Aparājītā, see Mallmann 1986, p. 103, concerning Parṇaśabarī, *ibidem*, p. 301.
- 22) Leoshko 1991, p. 233 & 1995, p. 50.
- 23) Liebert 1986, p. 134 quoted by Bautze-Picron 1995b, p. 74 note 5.
- 24) Losty 1990, p. 195, Pal 1993, p. 67. A similar image of the goddess is perhaps depicted on a leaf which once belonged to the Heeramaneck Galleries (Parke-Bernet 1964, cat. 185, pp. 50-51: second folio from top), but the poor quality of the photograph prevents us from being definitive about the identification.
- 25) A. Fouliet noticed that the artist only painted five arms on the proper right side and six on the proper left one (1900, p. 148 note 1).
- 26) Unfortunately also, Gorakshkar and Desai do not give any description of the paintings included in the manuscript where this illumination is inserted. From the black and white photograph which accompanies their article, one can only surmise the presence of some attributes: *aṅkuṣa* and *vajra* (left and right), bow and arrow (left and right), the noose held in the two lower hands and passing behind the back (see here app. 91), one left hand in front of the breast with perhaps the *tarjanīmudrā* and holding eventually

- the stalk of the flower which seems to be painted above the *aukaśa* and the lower right hand open in the *varadamudra* with perhaps an attribute.
- 27) These manuscript covers will be analysed in detail in the proceedings of the South Asian Archaeologists Conference, Leiden, July 1999.
- 28) Bautze-Pieron 1993, pp. 153 & 155.
- 29) Leoshko 1993/94, pp. 258-259. In the light of what J. Leoshko writes, it becomes clear that the event which took place at Vaiśālī is also related to what had happened at Bodhi Gayā: there, the Buddha decided to conquer "the final *māra* [i.e. *mṛtyumāra*] with his resolve to obtain nirvāṇa", i.e. he completed at Vaiśālī what had been begun at Bodhi Gayā (where he had conquered three of the four *māra*s).
- 30) Similarly, the Prajñāpāramitā is painted on the folio 2, surrounded by the two scenes of teaching which took place at Sārnāth and Srāvastī (Gorakṣīkar-Desai 1987, p. 563 & pl. III-b & IV).
- 31) B. Bhattacharyya 1968, vol. I, pp. 297-299.
- 32) *Sādhana* 135 (*ibidem*, pp. 278-279). See also Mallmann 1986, p. 265. *Sādhana* 145 introduces the Hindu deities "Hari, Hara, Brahmā..." (*ibidem*, p. 262) and the text 144 evokes in that position "the *upāya* and the *prajñā*" (above note 18).
- 33) Concerning this point, see Bautze-Pieron 1995b, notes 5, 46 & 75 and figs. 2, 3, 5-7, 16, 17 & 21 and figs. 8 & 18 where only the weapon is illustrated.
- 34) It is also an attribute of the Pañcarakṣā Mahāpratisarā (Mallmann 1986, p.291, *sādhana* 206). More could be apparently said about the similarities between this Protectress and Mārīcī, both belong indeed to the *kula* of Vairocana (the *caitya* can adorn the head-dress of the first deity (*ibidem*, p. 290) or between the solar goddess and certain other Rakṣās, Mahāmāyurī for instance who is related to the *aśoka* tree and is with Aśokakāntā Mārīcī an assistant of the Tārā (*ibidem*, pp. 290 & 292).
- 35) *Sādhana* 133 : *vairocanasānāthavatamamukūṭinī*. Various *sādhanas* (137, 138, 141 & 142 or a passage from the *Nispannayogāvalī* : Mallmann 1986, p. 263) underline that Mārīcī is affiliated to the *kula* of Vairocana (Mallmann 1986, p. 260 note 5). The relationship between the two has been variously appreciated : Liebert 1986, pp. 173-174, 316-317 & 320 considers the goddess as an emanation or as a "*śakti*" of Vairocana when she is named Vajradhātviśvarī (a name which occurs in the *sādhanas* 136). M. Ghosh 1980, p. 94 qualifies Vairocana as "lord" of Mārīcī, *kule śa* in the Sanskrit text, but does this word reflect the relation *upāya/prajñā*? Elsewhere (p. 78 and note 1), the authoress quotes Vairocana as being one of the "parental Dhyāni-Buddhas", also mentioned by her as being "spiritual sires".
- 36) Why the *aśoka* and not another tree? perhaps because this tree with fire red flowers is traditionnally related to the woman, blossoming when the latter hits it with her foot or perhaps because it is a medicinal plant used in the treatment of genital troubles? (Majumuria/Joshi 1988, pp. 106-108) Or perhaps also because it was the tree (among other ones mentioned in the tradition) below which the Buddha was born at Lumbini? The major position of the tree is also enhanced through its visualization, as it is described in the texts, which takes place in the meditation: out of this image, arises the initial letter of the deity's name from where emerges finally the goddess herself.
- 37) Viennot 1954, pp. 90 sqr.
- 38) The *caitya* as ornament of the head-dress is quoted in the *maṅḍala* 17 of the *Nispannayogāvalī*, which is devoted to the goddess (Mallmann 1986, p. 261). The Japanese depictions of the goddess preserve either the Jīna image or the *caitya* (L'Érudéric 1992, pp. 226-227).
- 39) Above note 8 (most of the images published by M. Bénisti as not representing Vairocana should in fact be identified with the latter).
- 40) Mallmann 1986, p. 301. In stone sculpture, the Obstacles are illustrated by the presence of the defeated Gaṇapati crawling on the ground, see Saraswati 1977, ill. 188-189 or Bhattachali 1929, pl. XXIII & pp. 58-61 e.g. On these images also, two further deities are illustrated, who are a male figure with apparently a horse-head, perhaps Hayagrīva (according to Bhattachali; he would be "the Hindu god of Fever" : Bhattacharyya 1958, p. 233) and Śītalā, who, as goddess of the small-pox, apparently symbolizes the Epidemics. Besides, the marks of the decease appear on the two corpses on which stand the goddess (Bhattachali 1929, p. 60) and which symbolize the Death of the text. Both goddesses appear also as two Dhāriṇīṣ following each other in a group of twelve located in the northern corner of a Mañjuśrī *maṅḍala* (Mallmann 1964, p. 87; 1986, p. 151) (in this text, she can at times be named Mārī, is red and has for attributes the needle with the thread - apart from the viśvavajra common to the twelve Dhāriṇīṣ).
- 41) Mallmann 1986, pp. 427 & 228, or even, she can sit above Kāmadeva and his wife, themselves depicted above Māra.
- 42) Mallmann 1986, p. 300-301.
- 43) Raghu Vira/Lokesh Candra 1962, pls. 84-85 (the Pañcarakṣās are illustrated on pl. 86-90, see also Mevissen 1989, S.IV.C).
- 44) Mallmann 1986, pp. 15, 292, 293, Mevissen 1989, pp. 15, 17, 18. This explains also the doubt expressed by P. Pal concerning the painting 79 (reference in the appendix).

- 45) Mevissen 1989, fig. 114 (12th c., Nepal), fig. 74 (16th c., Nepal) and perhaps fig. 93 (she half sits, half stands in a dancing position). This Rakṣī does not always sit in *vajra samā* like the other goddesses apparently, see also Mevissen 1989, fig. 94.
- 46) The two luminaries are noticed on either side of the Buddha depicted at his Enlightenment on a slab found at Jambhā, a village near Bodh Gayā (Panday 1918; Leoshko 1987, fig. 11 & pp. 39-40). The sun lying above the moon crescent becomes, from now onwards, a common motif observed above the *caitya.s* in Tibet or Nepal. See also Bautze-Pieron 1994, p. 150 and in particular note 48 where this motif of the combined luminaries is discussed in relation with the image of Viśvarūpa.
- 47) Even at a late period, the two astres can be preserved, crowning the *caitya* within which the deity stands, see *Cultural Relics*, 1992, pl. 80 & p.225 (eight-armed Mārīcī; seven sows are distributed in the front part of the pedestal, Rāhu appears below them, holding in the hands two circular disks, symbols of the moon and the sun which he has stolen : both are thus reconquered by the goddess).
- 48) For instance, on the illuminations of the Bodhi in the manuscript dated in the reign of Gopāla IV (previously III) which is preserved at the Museum of Fine Arts in Boston, see fig. 17 of Bautze-Pieron 1996. And very evidently, the Graha already appears on a sculptural fragment from Sarnath now in the Indian Museum (Foucher 1900, fig. 30 on p. 169; Anderson 1883, cat.S.60 pp. 29-31) within the group of eight or nine Graha.s forming a row below the depiction of the Parinirvāṇa; below them, a second row of deities like Śiva, Brahmā or Viṣṇu among others is also shown and above them two further gods are seen, Gaṇeśa and Skanda, each on their respective mount. All of them apparently mourn at the decease of the Buddha and do not thus show the vindicative mood which they betrayed while attacking the Buddha at Bodh Gayā when he attained the Bodhi or the Nirvāṇa. After he had reached at this psychic level also, all the ferocious gods and goddesses had to submit and thus underwent a change in their behaviour towards him.
- 49) Translation after Bhattacharyya 1958, pp. 210-211.
- 50) Bautze-Pieron 1996.
- 51) Apparently, she is identified with the sun or with the rays of the sun in Tibet according to the information provided with by Waddell 1934, p. 218 who states that "the monk, facing the sun [i.e. the East as stipulated in the *sādhanā*], and uplifting his right hand to a saluting posture, chants "It has arisen ! The sun of happiness has arisen ! The goddess Mārīcī has arisen ! Om-Mārīcīnam svāhā !" On repeating this *mantra* of Mārīcī seven times, he continues with: "Whenever I recall your name I am protected from all fear. I pray for the attainment of the great stainless bliss. I salute you, O goddess Mārīcī ! Bless me, and fulfil my desires. Protect me, O Goddess, from all the eight fears of foe, robbers, wild beasts, snakes, and poisons, weapons, firewater, and high precipices." "
- 52) The *makara* appears also below Aruṇa, the charioteer of Sūrya in the representations of the god made in Bengal (Haque 1992, pl. 163-166 & 171) or at Lakṣmī Sarai (Bautze-Pieron 1991/92, fig. 25 & p. 258 No. A.27). Haque (ibidem, p. 184) quotes the *Viśvakarmakalpa* according to which the chariot of Sūrya should carry an emblem shaped as a *makara*. The author is thus most probably right in identifying the face adorning the frontal part of the pedestal with this emblem. It is, however, not impossible that the presence of the aquatic monster could be related to the topic of the *kāla-makara*. Haque quotes also (note 45) the illustrations of the chariot shaped as a *makara* which supports Māra/Kama on various panels in terracotta from Pāhārpur (a fourth panel is preserved at the Asutosh Museum).
- 53) A *nāga* named Padmanābha draws the chariot of Sūrya : Vogel 1926, pp. 49, 84-87 and twelve great *nāga.s* can also present this function : ibidem, p. 284.
- 54) Above note 52.
- 55) Bautze-Pieron 1992a, fig. 36.2
- 56) Mallmann 1986, p. 263, *sādhanā.s* 132 & 135.
- 57) Leoshko 1988, fig. 1; Huntington 1979, figs. 1-3 or Sharma 1979, figs. 1-2.
- 58) Pal 1972, figs. 1-2 & 6. The "Burmese" image is also considered to be "Nepalese" by Sharma 1979, p. 128.
- 59) Piotrovsky 1993, cat. 2 pp. 106-109.
- 60) Mallmann 1948, pp. 186-191 & 1986, p. 107.
- 61) Bautze-Pieron 1989c about the origin of this image at Bodh Gayā in the 8th or 9th c. Mallmann 1986, pp. 107-108 notices also the similarities between the images of Mañjuśrī and Avalokiteśvara. See Leoshko 1987, pp. 228-253 concerning Avalokiteśvara Siṃhanāḍa at Bodh Gayā (& her figs. 113-114 & 116-117). The same author quotes pp. 35 & 251, a 12th c. inscription which proves the cult of this form of the Bodhisatva at the site.
- 62) Mallmann 1986, pp. 252 & 253; Mallmann 1964, pp. 23-26 (Mañjuśrī) and previous note (Avalokiteśvara). And some authors apply the name of the latter to the first one (quoted by Mallmann 1964, p. 44). Leoshko 1987, pp. 252-253 underlines that Siṃhanāḍa Lokeśvara is "related to the power of Buddhist doctrine".
- 63) First of all, most of the numerous images of the teaching Buddha, located at Kanheri, Ajanta or in the other sites of the region.
- 64) In the *Sarvatathāgatavasanīgraha*, Sākyamuni, also named Vairocana or Vajradhāta, is installed by all Tathāgata.s at the top of Mount Meru on a lion throne and facing all directions (Snellgrove 1987, p. 242).
- 65) Wayman/Tajima 1992, p. 101 : the Japanese tradition names him "brilliant everywhere": Wayman further adds that "he is said to

be surr
66) For v
Tajima
p. 6.
67) Way
light.
p. 323
by the
68) Das
69) Elia
70) Das
71) Das
72) Das
73) Wa
74) Way
his st
at EL
cons
reali
text
75) W
76) M
77) B
relat
78) Th
com
Val
on t
pres
Val
ord
Val
285

Abbr
AR =
ASZ =

Allin
Th
C
ec
/U
And
C
C
Ann
Ann
Spo
ASH

- be surrounded by various colored rays; and "Wheel of Syllables" chapter says those are burning rays."
- 66) For what follows, I am indebted to the writings of S.B. Dasgupta 1974 & 1976 and of Alex Wayman 1977 & 1992 (with R. Tajima). But, the light inherent to the personality of the Buddha is already a major element in the *Mahāvastu*, Bautze-Pieron 1998b, p. 6.
- 67) Wayman 1977, pp. 322-323; see also his table of equivalences p. 324. The first text speaks, as a matter of fact, of four natures of light, adding that "... in an instant free from darkness, there is Clear Light ... which one sees with the Eye of Knowledge ..." (*ibidem*, p. 323), it is also that "Sun of knowledge" (*jñānasūrya*) which rises "with crystalline appearance ... through union of *vajra* and *padma* by the yogin ..."
- 68) Dasgupta 1974, pp. 43-44, 155-157. Concerning the opposition *Rāhu/kālāgni*, see Dasgupta 1976, pp. 97 & 235sq.
- 69) Eliade 1972, pp. 237sq.
- 70) Dasgupta 1974, p. 155.
- 71) Dasgupta 1977, p. 44, Wayman 1977, pp. 191 & 274 (where this sublime light is assimilated with the hermaphrodit).
- 72) Dasgupta 1977, p. 44.
- 73) Wayman 1977, p. 191.
- 74) Wayman 1992, pp. xiii & 11-12 proposed the 6th c., probably by comparison with the information given by John C. Huntington in his study of the caves 6 & 7 at Aurangabad although he does not expressively mention this site. Wayman refers to the caves 11 & 12 at Ellora which are later (7th-8th c.). According to the writer, the text must have influenced the artistic realisation. But taking into consideration the information collected at Aurangabad or at Nasik (cave 23, see Bautze-Pieron [in the press]) and which are earlier realisations of the 6th c., one can suppose that the conception of the *maṇḍala* found approximately at the same period its way in the text and in the stone.
- 75) Wayman 1992, p. 126.
- 76) Mallmann 1986, pp. 102 (Aparājitā) & 303-305 (Prajñāntaka).
- 77) Bautze-Pieron 1995/96, p. 373 & note 85. The characters of Aparājitā, Vasudhāra or Uṣṇṣivijayā are also presented there in their relation to the Enlightenment (pp. 373-376).
- 78) This information is traced in the description of the *maṇḍala* of the *Mahāvairocana-sūtra/Vairocana-bhūsanbodhitantra*: the text considers that the nature of the Vairocana of the *kāyamaṇḍala* is placed at the level of the *sambhogakāya* whereas the one of the Vairocana of the *cittamaṇḍala* is related to the *dharma-kāya*. Now, in the *Garbhamāṇḍala*, the second *maṇḍala* has been superposed on the first one; these are thus the very same two essences which are both found in Vairocana in the *Garbhamāṇḍala*, that are also present in Māricī (Wayman 1992, p. 95). Besides, the *Śarvatathā gatautivasan-grāha* was promulgated by Śākyamuni as Vairocana. After having reached five successive levels of Enlightenment, Śākyamuni became Vairocana and came back on earth in order to defeat Māra. There is thus here a direct filiation, if not even a confusion in the personalities, between Śākyamuni and Vairocana (Snellgrove 1987, pp. 120-121). The historical Buddha is already named Vairocana in the *Mahāvastu* (Jones 1952 II, p. 285 note 4).

Bibliography

Abbreviations

AR = Annual Report.

ASI = Archaeological Survey of India

Allinger, Eva [1997]

The Green Tārā in the Ford Collection: Some Iconographical Remarks, *South Asian Archaeology 1995. Proceedings of the 13th Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists, Cambridge, 5-9 (sic!, correct in: 3-7) July, 1995*, volume 2, eds. Raymond Allchin and Bridget Allchin with the assistance of Gill Elston and Oleg Starza-Majewski, New Delhi / Calcutta / U.S.A., 1997, pp. 665-671.

Anderson, John [1883]

Catalogue and Hand-Book of the Archaeological Collections in the Indian Museum, Part II, Gupta and Inscription Galleries, Calcutta, 1883.

Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey, Eastern Circle, for 1907-1908, Calcutta, 1908.

Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India, 1919-1920, ed. John Marshall, Calcutta, 1922; *ibidem*, 1922-23, ed. D. Brainerd Spooner, Calcutta, 1924; *ibidem*, 1923-24, ed. John Marshall, Calcutta, 1926.

Asher, Frederick M. [1970]

- The Former Broadley Collection, Bihar Sharif. *Artibus Asiae*. XXXII, 2/3, 1970, pp. 105-124.
- Bandyopadhyay, Bima [1981]
Metal Sculpture of Eastern India. Delhi, 1981.
- Banerji, R.D. [1933]
Eastern Indian School of Mediaeval Sculpture. Delhi, 1933.
- Basak, Radhagovinda et Bhattacharyya, Dinesh Chandra [1919]
A Catalogue of the Archaeological Relics in the Museum of the Varānda Research Society. Rajshahi, Rajshahi, 1919.
- Bautze-Picron, Claudine [1989a]
 Identification d'images biharies reproduites dans la collection Buchanan Hamilton conservée à l'India Office Library and Records. *Berliner Indologische Studien*. Band 4/5, 1989, pp. 269-325.
- [1989b]
 Review of : Paul, Debjani, *The Art of Nālandā, Development of Buddhist Sculpture, 600-1200 A.D.*, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Leiden, 1987. Enschede: Quick Service Drukkerij, 1987. *Tribus, Jahrbuch des Linden-Museums*. Band 38, 1989, pp. 196-198.
- [1989c]
 Some Aspects of Mañjuśrī's Iconography in Bihar from the 7th century onwards. *Tribus, Jahrbuch des Linden-Museums*. Stuttgart, Band 38, 1989, pp. 71-90.
- [1991/92]
 Lakhī Sarai, an Indian Site of Late Buddhist Iconography and its Position within the Asian Buddhist World. *Silk Road Art and Archaeology*, Kamakura, vol. 2, 1991/92, pp. 239-284.
- [1992a]
 A Preliminary Report on the Buddha Image from Betagi. *South Asian Archaeology 1989. Papers from the Tenth International Conference of South Asian Archaeologists in Western Europe. Musée National des Arts Asiatiques Guimet, Paris, France, 3-7 July 1989*, ed. Catherine Jarrige et alii. Madison, Wisconsin, 1992, pp. 301-308.
- [1992b]
 The 'Stele' in Bihar and Bengal, 8th to 12th Centuries - Symmetry and Composition. *Indian Art and Archaeology*, edited by Ellen M. Raven and Karel R. van Kooij. (Panels of the VIIIth World Sanskrit Conference, Leiden, August 1987, vol. X), Leiden, 1992, pp. 3-34.
- [1993]
 Crying Leaves, Some Remarks on 'The Art of Pāla India (8th-12th Centuries) and Its International Legac'. *East and West*, vol. 43, 1993, pp. 277-294.
- [1994]
 The "Viṣṇu-Lokēśvara" Images from Bengal. An Eastern Version of Viśvarūpa According to the Pāñcarātra ?. *Festschrift Klaus Bruhn zur Vollendung des 65. Lebensjahres dargebracht von Schülern, Freunden und Kollegen*, ed. Nalinī Balbir & Joachim K. Bautze, Reinbeck, 1994, pp. 129-170.
- [1995a]
 The Art of Eastern India in the Avery Brundage Collection. Asian Art Museum of San Francisco. *Arts of Asia*, vol. 25, No. 4, July-August 1995, pp. 46-56.
- [1995b]
 Between men and gods, small motifs in the Buddhist art of Eastern India, an interpretation. *Function and Meaning in Buddhist Art. Proceedings of a seminar held at Leiden University, 21-24 October 1991*, ed. K.R. van Kooij & H. van der Veere, Groningen, 1995, pp. 59-79.
- [1995/96]
 Śākyamuni in Eastern India and Tibet in the 11th to the 13th Centuries. *Silk Road Art and Archaeology*, vol. 4, 1995/96, pp. 355-408.
- [1996]
 From God to Demon, from Demon to God : Brahmā and other Hindu Deities in late Buddhist Art of Eastern India. *Journal of the Art of Bengal*. Dhaka, vol. 1, pp. 109-135.
- [1997]
 Le groupe des Huit Grands Bodhisattva en Inde : genèse et développement. *Living a Life in Accord with Dhamma : Papers in Honor of Professor Jean Boisselier on his Eightieth Birthday*, eds. Natasha Eilenberg, M.S. Subhadradis Diskul, Robert L. Brown. Bangkok, 1997, pp. 1-55.

- [1998a]
The Art of Eastern India in the collection of the Museum für Indische Kunst, Berlin – Stone and Terracotta Sculptures, Berlin : Monographien zur Indischen Archäologie, Kunst und Philologie, Band 12.
- [1998b] add : see page attacked
- [1999]
 Buddhist Painting during the Reign of Harivarmadeva (end of the 11th century c.) in southeast Bangladesh. *Journal of Bengal Art*, vol. 4, 1999, pp. 159-197.
- [in the press]
 Nasik : The Late Mahāyāna Caves 2, 15, 20 & 23-24, *South Asian Archaeology 1997, Papers from the Fourteenth International Conference of South Asian Archaeologists in Europe, Museo Nazionale dell'Arte Orientale, Roma, Italia, 7-11 July 1997*, ed. M. Taddei, A.-M. Quagliotti et alii.
- Beal, S. [1881]
 Two Chinese-Buddhist Inscriptions found at Buddha Gayā, *Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, October 1881, pp. 552-572.
- Behring, S. [1943]
 Marici-Figuren des Berliner Völkerkunde Museums im Rahmen eines Ikonographischen Versuchs, *Baessler Archiv*, Band XXV, 1943, pp. 1-23.
- Bénisti, Mireille [1991]
 Au Sujet de Représentations Indiennes de Vairocana et de ses Mudrā, *Akṣayanīvrī, Essays Presented to Dr. Debata Mitra in Abinitiation of her scholarly Contributions*, ed. Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Delhi, 1991, pp. 259-267.
- Bhattacharyya, Benoytosh [1924/1958]
The Indian Buddhist Iconography, Mainly Based on The Sādhnamālā and Cognate Tāntric Texts of Rituals, 1st ed., Calcutta, 1924, 2d ed., Calcutta, 1958.
- [1932/1964]
An Introduction to Buddhist Esoterism, Varanasi, 1962 (Chowkhamba Sanskrit Studies, vol. XLVI).
- , ed. [1968]
Sādhnamālā, Baroda, 1968 (Gadkwar's Oriental Series 26 & 41).
- Bhattacharyya, D.C. [1964]
 An interesting image of the goddess Mārīcī, *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress, Ranchi Session*, 1964, pp. 91-94.
- [1974]
 Brahmanīyadeva-Viṣṇu : A Composite Form of Viṣṇu and Kārtikeya, *Journal of the Varendra Research Museum*, vol. 4, 1974, pp. 13-25.
- [1978]
Studies in Buddhist Iconography, New Delhi, 1978.
- [1979/1980]
Iconology of Composite Images, Delhi, 1979/1980.
- Bhattasali, N.K. [1929]
Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum, Dacca, 1929.
- Bloch, Theodor [1911]
Supplementary Catalogue of the Archaeological Collection of the Indian Museum, Calcutta, 1911.
- Broadley, Alexander Merrick [1872]
Ruins of the Nālanda Monasteries, at Burgaon, Sud-Division Bihar, Zilla Patna, Calcutta, 1872.
- Buddha [1967]
Buddha und seine Zeit, Wiesbaden, 1967.
- Burgess, James [1897]
The Ancient Monuments, Temples and Sculptures of India, Illustrated in a Series of Reproductions of Photographs in the India Office, Calcutta Museum, and other Collections, With Descriptive Notes and References, London, 2 vols., 1897.
- Chanda, Ramaprasad [1929]
Bhānja Dynasty of Mayurbhanj and their Ancient Capital Khiching, Mayurbhanj, 1929.
- Chhavi
Chhavi, Golden Jubilee Volume, Bharat Kala Bhavan 1920-1970, Benares, 1971.
- Cultural Relics [1992]

- Cultural Relics of Tibetan Buddhism Collected in the Qing Palace*, Beijing, 1992.
- Cunningham, Alexander [1892]
Makabodhi or the Great Buddhist Temple Under the Bodhi Tree at Buddha-Gaya, London, 1892.
- Dani, Ahmad Hasan [1959]
Buddhist Sculpture in East Pakistan, Karachi, 1959.
- Das Gupta, P.C. [1963]
Archaeological Discovery in West Bengal, *A Bulletin of the Directorate of Archaeology West Bengal*, No. 1, Calcutta, 1963.
- Dasgupta, Shashi Bhushan [1974]
An Introduction to Tāntric Buddhism, Calcutta, 3rd ed., 1974.
— [1976]
Obscure Religious Cults, (reprint:) Calcutta, 1976.
- Donaldson, Thomas [1985]
Orissan Images of Aṣṭabhujāpīṭa Mārīci, *Journal of Orissa Research Society*, Vol. 3, 1985, pp. 35-44.
- Eliade, Mircea [1972]
Le yoga, immortalité et liberté, Paris, 1972.
- See paper attached.
- Foucher, Alfred [1900]
Étude sur l'iconographie bouddhique de l'Inde d'après des documents nouveaux, Paris, 1900.
— [1905]
Étude sur l'iconographie bouddhique de l'Inde d'après des textes inédits, Paris, 1905.
- Frédéric, Louis [1992]
Les Dieux du Bouddhisme. Guide iconographique, Paris, 1992.
- 5000 Jahre [1962]
5000 Jahre Kunst in Pakistan, Eine Ausstellung des Deutschen Kunstrates, Darmstadt/Augsburg/Bonn, 1962.
- Ghosh, Mallar [1980]
Development of Buddhist Iconography in Eastern India: A Study of Tāra, Prakṛjñās of Five Tathāgatas and Bhṛkūṭi, New Delhi, 1980.
- Goetz, Herman [1966]
Pāla-Sena Schools, *Encyclopaedia of World Art*, vol. XI, col. 21-37, New York-Toronto-London, 1966.
- Gorakshkar, Sadashiv & Desai, Kalpana [1987]
"An Illustrated Manuscript of *Ashvasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā* in The Asiatic Society of Bombay", in *Orientalia Iosephi Tucci memoriae dicata*, eds. G. Gnoli & L. Lanciotti, Roma, vol. II, 561-568.
- Grünwedel, Albert [1900]
Mythologie du Buddhismes au Tibet et en Mongolie basée sur la collection lamannique du Prince Oukhtomsky, Leipzig, 1900.
- Gupta, P.L. [1965]
Patna Museum Catalogue of Antiquities (Stone Sculptures, Metal Images, Terracottas and Minor Antiquities), Patna, 1965.
- Haque, Enamul [1992]
Bengal Sculptures, Hindu Iconography upto c. 1250 A.D., Dhaka, 1992.
- Harle, James C. [1977]
Remarks on *Āṅgika Mahayanist Art after 900 A.D.*, ed. William Watson, *Colloquies on Art & Archaeology in Asia No. 2*, Londres, [reprint:] 1977, pp. 10-16.
- Huntington, John C. [1981]
Cave Six at Aurangabad: A Tantrayana Monument 2, *Kalādarśana, American Studies in the Art of India*, ed. Joanna G. Williams, New Delhi, 1981, pp. 47-55.
— [1987]
Pilgrimage as Image: The Cult of the *Aṣṭamahāprātihārya*, Part II, The Great Stele at Jagdīspur and the Presumed Locus of the Cult, *Orientalia*, vol. 18, 8, 1987, pp. 56-68.
- Huntington, Susan L. [1979]
Some Bronzes from Patelpur, Gaya, *Oriental Art*, vol. XXV, 2, 1979, pp. 240-247.
— [1984]
The "Pāla-Sena" Schools of Sculpture, Leyde, 1984.
- Huntington, Susan L. & Huntington, John C. [1989]

- Leaves from the *Bodhi Tree* : The Art of Pāla India (8th-12th Centuries) and Its International Legacy, *Orientalia*, vol. 20, no. 10, octobre 1989, pp. 26-46.
- [1990]
- Leaves from the Bodhi Tree : The Art of Pāla India (8th-12th centuries) and Its International Legacy*. Seattle & Londres, 1990.
- Jones, J.I. [1949-1952-1956]
- The Mahāvastu*, translated from the Buddhist Sanskrit, Sacred Books of the East, volumes XVI, XVIII, XIX, Londres, 1949 (volume I), 1952 (volume II), 1956 (volume III).
- Keith, E.W. [1910]
- Notes on Some Buddhist Remains in Magadha, *Bengal, Past & Present*, vol. VI, July-September 1910, pp. 57-68.
- Kirfel, Willibald [1948]
- Die dreiköpfige Gottheit, Archäologisch-ethnologischer Streifzug durch die Ikonographie der Religionen*. Bonn, 1948.
- Krishna Murthy, K. [1989]
- Sculptures of Vajrayana Buddhism*, Delhi, 1989.
- Lefebvre d'Argencé, René & Tse Bartholomew, Terese [1969]
- Indian and South-East Asian Stone Sculptures from the Avery Brundage Collection*. Pasadena, 1969.
- Leoshko, Janice [1987]
- The Iconography of Buddhist Sculptures of the Pāla and Sena Periods from Bodhgaya*. Ph.D. Thesis, The Ohio State University, Columbus, 1987.
- [1988]
- The Vajrasana Buddha, *Bodhgaya, the site of enlightenment*, ed. Janice Leoshko, Bombay, 1988, pp. 29-44.
- [1991]
- The implications of Bodhgaya's Sūrya as a Symbol of Enlightenment, *Akṣayanūṭī, Essays presented to Dr. Debala Mitra in admiration of her scholarly contributions*, ed. Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Delhi, 1991, pp. 231-234.
- [1993/94]
- Scenes of the Buddha's Life in Pāla-Period Art, *Silk Road Art and Archaeology*, vol. 3, 1993/94, pp. 251-276.
- [1995]
- Pilgrimage and the evidence of Bodhgaya's images, *Function and Meaning in Buddhist Art, Proceedings of a seminar held at Leiden University 21-24 October 1991*, ed. K.R. van Kooij & H. van der Veere, Groningen, 1995, pp. 45-57.
- Liebert, Gösta [1986]
- Iconographic Dictionary of the Indian Religions, Hinduism - Buddhism - Jainism*, Delhi, 2d ed., 1986.
- Longhurst, A.H. [1919-1920]
- Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India for the Year 1919-1920*, pp. 35-
- Losty, Jeremiah P. [1982]
- The Art of the Book in India*, London, 1982.
- [1989]
- An Early Indian Manuscript of the Karaṇḍavyūhasūtra, *Nalinikānta Śaravāṛī, Dr. N.K. Bhattacharya Centenary Volume (1888-1988), Studies in Art and Archaeology of Bihar and Bengal*, ed. Debala Mitra & Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Delhi, 1989, pp. 1-21.
- [1990]
- The 'Vredenburg Manuscript' in the Victoria and Albert Museum, *Mukavandā, Essays in honour of Dr. James C. Harle*, ed. Claudine Bautze-Pieron, Delhi, 1990, pp. 189-199.
- MacDonald, Ariane [1962]
- Le mandala du Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa*. Paris, 1962.
- Majumdar, R.C. [1971]
- The History of Bengal, vol. I, Hindu Period*, (reprint :) Patna, 1971.
- Majumdar, Trilok Chandra & Joshi, D.P. [1988]
- Religious & Useful Plants of Nepal & India (Medicinal Plants and Flowers as mentioned in Religious Myths and Legends of Hinduism and Buddhism)*, Gwalior, 1988.
- Mallebrein, Cornelia [1984]
- Skulpturen aus Indien, Bedeutung und Form*, Staatliches Museum für Völkerkunde, München, 1984.
- Mallmann, Marie-Thérèse de [1948]
- Introduction à l'étude d'Avalokiteśvara*, Paris, 1948.
- [1964]

- Étude iconographique sur Mañjuśrī*. Paris, 1964.
— [1969]
Notes d'iconographie tantrique. IV. À propos de Vajravārāhī. *Arts Asiatiques*, vol. XX, 1969, pp. 21-40.
— [1986]
Introduction à l'iconographie du bouddhisme tantrique. (reprint) Paris, 1986.
- Marc Erythraeum [1998]
Mare Erythraeum, Band II : Indien. Reigen der Götter. Staatliches Museum für Völkerkunde München, 1998.
- Meisezahl, R.O. [1965-66]
Die Göttin Vajravārāhī. Eine ikonographische Studie nach einem Sādhana-Text von Advayavajra. *Oriens*, vol. 18-19, 1965-1966, pp. 228-303.
- Mevissen, Gerd J.R. [1989]
Iconographie der Pañcarakṣī-s. Eine Studie über Ursprung und Verbreitung der bildlichen Darstellung der fünf weiblichen Schutzgottheiten im nördlichen Buddhismus. Berlin. (Schriftliche Magister-Hausarbeit. Fachbereich 14 der Freien Universität Berlin).
— [1991/92]
The Indian Connection : Images of Deified Spells in the Arts of Northern Buddhism, Part II. *Silk Road Art and Archaeology*, vol. 2, 1991/92, pp. 351-382.
- Mitra, Debala [1981]
Ramagiri (1958-61). New Delhi, 1981.
- Mitra Mallar [1998]
Image of Mārīcī found in the Museum of Calcutta. *Studies in Architecture in Archaeology, Papers presented in memory of P.C. Dasgupta*. ed. Asok Datta. New Delhi, 1998, pp. 343-354.
- Mitra, Sisi Kumar, ed. [1979]
East Indian Bronzes. Calcutta, 1979.
- Mohapatra, R.P. [1986]
Archaeology in Orissa (sites and monuments). Delhi, 1986.
- Pal, Pratapaditya [1972]
The Story of a Wandering Bronze Buddha - and Two American Examples. *The Connoisseur*, vol. 181, no. 1-2, 1972, pp. 203-207.
— [1988]
Indian Sculpture, Volume 2, 700-1800, A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection, Los Angeles, 1988.
— [1993]
Indian Painting, A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection, Volume 1, 1000-1700, Los Angeles, 1993.
- Pāla Stone Sculpture*. Asian Art Museum of San Francisco January 23-April 10, 1984. San Francisco, 1984.
- Panday, H. [1918]
The Jāmbighā Inscrption. *Journal of the Bihar and Orissa Research Society*, vol. 4, 1918, pp. 273-280.
- Parke-Bernet Galleries Inc. [1964]
Indian Sculptures, Paintings, Bronzes, Ancient Art of the Near and far East from the collections of the Heeramaneck Galleries. Public Auction, 14 October 1964 (Sale number 2298).
- Patry Leidy, Denise & Robert A.F. Thurman [1998]
Mandala, The Architecture of Enlightenment. New York, 1998.
- Paul, Debjani [1995]
The Art of Nālandā, Development of Buddhist Sculpture, 600-1200 A.D.. Delhi, 1995 (reproduction verbatim of her Ph.D. thesis, reviewed by Bautze-Picron 1989b).
- Petrovsky, Mikhail, ed. [1993]
Lost Empire of the Silk Road. Buddhist Art from Khara Khoto (X-XIIIth century). Milan, 1993.
- Raghu Vira & Lokesh Candra [1962]
A New Tibeto-Mongol Pantheon, Part 2, New Delhi, 1962.
- Ram, Rajendra [1990-1992]
Heretic Motifs in Mārīcī : The Sun Goddess of Buddhism : A.D. 700 - 1400. *The Journal of The Bihar Research Society, Platinum Jubilee Volume*, vols. LXXVI-LXXVIII, 1990-1992, pp. 231-238.
- Ray, Nihar Ranjan, Khandalavala, Karl & Gorakshkar, Sadashiv [1986]
Eastern Indian Bronzes. New Delhi, 1986.

Ricca, F.
The G
Sahai, B.
Icono
Sahni, L.
Catal
Sahu, N.
Budd
Sankali
The t
Sarasw
Tantr
— [19
Pāy
Schroe
Indo
Sengup
Bud
Sengup
Trec
Sharm
Pāla
Sinha
Bhe
Smith
A I
Snell
Ina
Sothe
Subra
Sa
Tantr
Ta
Di
Tse L
"T
B
PF
Tuc
T
Vas
T
Vie
L
Vog
E
—
I
—
L
Wa

- Ricca, Franco & Erberto Lo Bue [1993]
The Great Stupa of Gyantse. A Complete Tibetan Pantheon of the Fifteenth century, London, 1993.
- Sahai, Bhagwani [1975]
Iconography of minor Hindu and Buddhist Deities, New Delhi, 1975.
- Sahni, Daya Ram [1972]
Catalogue of the Museum of Archaeology at Sarnath, with an introduction by J.Ph. Vogel, (reprint :), Delhi-Varanasi, 1972.
- Sahu, N.K. [1958]
Buddhism in Orissa, Utkal, 1958.
- Sankalia, H. D. [1972]
The University of Nalanda, Delhi, 1972.
- Saraswati, S.K. [1977]
Tantrayana Art, An Album, Calcutta, 1977.
- [1978]
Pāyuger Cītrakālā, Calcutta, 1978.
- Schroeder, Ulrich von [1981]
Indo-Tibetan Bronzes, Hong Kong, 1981.
- Sengupta, Anasua [1993]
Buddhist Art of Bengal (From the 3rd Century B.C. To The 13th Century A.D.), Delhi, 1993.
- Sengupta, Gautam [1991]
Treasures of the State Archaeological Museum, West Bengal, vol. 2, Calcutta, 1991.
- Sharma, Brijendra Nath [1979]
 Pāla Bronzes from Fatehpur, Gaya, *East and West*, vol. 29, 1979, pp. 127-130.
- Sinha, Vindhyesvarīprasād [1958]
Bhāratīya kalā ko bhār kī dena, Patna, 1958.
- Smith, Vincent A. [1969]
A History of Fine Art in India & Ceylon, third edition revised and enlarged by Karl Khandalavala, Bombay, 1969.
- Snellgrove, David [1987]
Indo-Tibetan Buddhism, Indian Buddhists and Their Tibetan Successors, London, 1987.
- Soldheby's auction catalogues: 26.11.1984 & 24.4.1990, London; 5.10.1990 & 5.12.1992, New York.
- Sūbrāhmanyam, R. [1964]
Salihundam, A Buddhist Site in Andhra Pradesh, Hyderabad, 1964.
- Tantrische Kunst des Buddhismus [1981]
Tantrische Kunst des Buddhismus, Eine Ausstellung unter der Schirmherrschaft des Senators für Kulturelle Angelegenheiten Dr. Dieter Sauberzweig, Kunstant Berlin-Tempelhof, Berlin, 1981.
- Tse Bartholomew, Terese [1989]
 "Taming of the Elephant" and Other Pāla Sculptures in the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco, *Studies in Art and Archaeology of Bihar and Bengal, Dr. N.K. Bhattasali Centenary Volume (1888-1988)*, ed. Debala Mitra & Gouriswar Bhattacharya, Delhi, 1989, pp.61-65.
- Tucci, Giuseppe [1973]
Transhimalaya, London, 1973.
- Vasu, Nahendrenāth [1911]
The Archaeological Survey of Mayurabhanja, Calcutta, 1911.
- Viennot, Odette [1954]
Le culte de l'arbre dans l'Inde ancienne, Paris, 1954.
- Vogel, Jean Philippe [1903-04]
 Buddhist Sculptures from Benares, *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India for the Years 1903-04*, pp. 212-226.
- [1926]
Indian Serpent-Lore or The Nāgas in Hindu Legend and Art, London, 1926.
- [1932]
De Buddhistische Kunst von Voor-Indië, Amsterdam, 1932.
- Waddell, L. Austine [1934]
The Buddhism of Tibet or Lamaism with its mystic Cults, Symbolism and Mythology, and in its Relation to Indian Buddhism.

second edition, Cambridge, 1934.

Wayman, Alex [1977]

Yoga of The Guhyasamajatantra, The Arcane Lore of Forty Verses, A Buddhist Tantra Commentary. Delhi, 1977.

Wayman, Alex & Tajima, R. [1992]

The Enlightenment of Vairocana. Book I. Study of the Vairocanaḥśambodhitantra [Alex Wayman]. *Book II. Study of the Mahavairocana-Sūtra* [R. Tajima]. Delhi, 1992.

Yi-Lian, Chou [1945]

Tantrism in China. *Harvard Journal of Asiatic Studies*, Vol. 8, March 1945, pp. 241-332.

— [1998b]

Lumière et obscurité: L'Éveil de Śākyamunī (Shākyamuni) et la victoire sur Māra (Māra). *Annali dell'Istituto Universitario Orientale*. Naples, Vol. 58, 1/2, 1998, pp. 1-49.

Zwalf, Wladimir, ed. [1985]

Buddhism, Art and Faith. London, 1985.

Fig. 1. Mārīcī
Berlin. Photo
Kunst Berlin

Fig. 3. Mārīcī

Fig. 1. Mārīcī (app.7). Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin. Photo courtesy of Museum für Indische Kunst Berlin.

Fig. 2. Mārīcī (app.11). René Russek collection, Zürich. Photo courtesy of René Russek.

Fig. 3. Mārīcī (app.13). Itkhauri. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 4. Mārīcī (app.14). Asian Art Museum of San Francisco, The Avery Brundage Collection. Photo courtesy of Asian Art Museum of San Francisco.

Fig. 5. Mārīcī (app.15), Lucknow Museum.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 6. Mārīcī (app.18), Nālandā Museum.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 7. Mārīcī (app.20), Nālandā Museum. Photo courtesy of
Archaeological Survey of India.

Fig. 8. Mārīcī (app.23), Nālandā Museum. Photo courtesy of
Archaeological Survey of India.

Fig. 10. Mārīcī (app.26). Stela at Jagdišpur-Nālandā. detail. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 9. Mārīcī (app.27). Stela at Jagdišpur-Nālandā. detail. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 11. Lower part of the stela at Jagdišpur-Nālandā.

Fig. 12. Vārāhī. Stela at Jagdišpur-Nālandā. detail. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 13. Pañcatathāgata. upper part of the stela at Jagdišpur-Nālandā. Indian Museum, Calcutta. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 14. Mārīcī (app.31), Ghosrāvān. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 15. Mārīcī (app.32), Tetrāvān. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 16. Mārīcī (app.51), Günter Heil collection, Berlin. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 17. Mārīcī (app.33), Indian Museum, Calcutta. Photo Cl. Bautze-Picron.

Fig. 18. Mārīcī (app.35). State Archaeological Museum of West Bengal, Calcutta. Photo courtesy of Archaeological Survey of India.

Fig. 19. Mārīcī (app.45). Mainamati Museum. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 20. Mārīcī (app.47). Private collection, Basel. Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 21. Mārīcī (app.48). National Museum of Bangladesh. Photo Cl. Bautze-Pieron.

Fig. 21-a. Detail

Fig. 21-b. Detail

Fig. 22. Mārīcī (app.82)
The British Library, London.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 23. Mārīcī (app.83-M).
The British Library, London.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 24. Paṃśābarī (app.83-P).
The British Library, London.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 25. Mārīcī (app.86-M).
The British Library, London.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 26. Parṇāsābarī (app.86-P).
The British Library, London.
Photo Joachim K. Bautze.

Fig. 27. Marīcī (app.85-M).
Los Angeles County Museum
of Art.
Photo courtesy of Los Angeles
County Museum of Art.

Fig. 28. Parṇāsābarī (app.85-P).
Los Angeles County Museum
of Art.
Photo courtesy of Los Angeles
County Museum of Art.

Errata

(Cl. Bautze-Picron, „Between Śākyamuni and Vairocana...“)

- p. 264, 5th line from bottom, read „elaboration“
 - p. 265, 10th line from bottom, read „already“; 5th line from bottom, read „dhāraṇīs“
 - p. 266, 12th line from bottom, read „illustrating“
 - p. 269, 4th line from bottom, drop „and is summarized at the end of this paper“
 - p. 270, 14th line from top, read „sūryamaṇḍala“
 - p. 271, 8th line from top, read „pertakes“
 - p. 272, 21st line from top, read „Jagdiśpur“
 - p. 297, 4th line from top, read „[1998b], Lumière et obscurité: L'Éveil de Śākyamuni et la victoire sur Māra, *Annali dell'Istituto Universitario Orientale*, Naples, vol. 58, 1/2, 1998, pp. 1-49.“
-